

CAN LONG PREGNANCY INTERVALS RESET THE EFFECT OF MATERNAL GENES?

Master's Degree Project in Bioscience, 30 ECTS

2025-01-16 – 2025-08-15

Ágnes Judit Juhász

Name of the external supervisors:

Karin Ytterberg and
Dr Pol Solé-Navais
Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology,
Institute of Clinical Sciences,
Sahlgrenska Academy, University of Gothenburg

SAHLGRENSKA ACADEMY

Examiner: Dr Sanja Jurcevic

School of Bioscience University of Skövde
Box 408
541 28 Skövde

Abstract

The length of pregnancy is a major determinant of newborn health and varies due to both environmental and genetic influences, yet their combined effects are not fully understood. The purpose of this thesis was to examine whether the time interval between pregnancies and a history of miscarriage alter maternal genetic influences on the timing of delivery. The study analysed pregnancies from women with more than one previous birth for the interpregnancy interval models and first pregnancies for the miscarriage models, using full-genome genotype information and polygenic scores that summarise the inherited contribution to pregnancy duration. Statistical evaluation was performed with linear regression and genome-wide tests of gene–environment interaction. The results showed that maternal genetic effects on gestational duration did not differ substantially across interpregnancy interval categories, although genetic influences were somewhat stronger at intermediate intervals. A notable interaction was detected at a genetic region near the gene *ATRNL1*, where the effect of the maternal allele was stronger among women with a previous miscarriage, and additional evidence pointed to a miscarriage-associated pattern of genetic variation at the *DPYSL3* locus. These findings indicate that maternal reproductive history can modify the expression of specific genetic factors that contribute to pregnancy timing and underline the need for future research integrating molecular data from relevant reproductive tissues.

Keywords: gestational duration; interpregnancy interval; miscarriage; genome-wide association study; *ATRNL1*; *DPYSL3*

Popular scientific summary

How maternal genetics and reproductive history influence preterm birth risk

Many biological processes determine the length of pregnancy, yet the origins of large individual variation remain incompletely understood. This research examines how maternal genetic effects interact with two important and often overlooked environmental factors: pregnancy interval and history of miscarriage.

Many small genetic factors work together to influence how long a pregnancy lasts. Polygenic scores and genome-wide gene–environment studies in large genetic datasets are used to capture such complexity. Preterm birth remains one of the most difficult conditions to manage in the context of global neonatal morbidity and mortality. These approaches also help estimate how much a person’s genetic background contributes to shorter or longer pregnancies.

Birth spacing is the period between the end of one pregnancy and conception of the subsequent one and is an important factor in the length of a pregnancy and maternal health. Clinical studies have shown that both shortened and prolonged birth spacing are associated with an increased risk of adverse pregnancy outcomes such as preterm birth, low birth weight, and maternal and neonatal complications. These research findings suggest that pregnancy and childbearing represent a considerable burden on the maternal body. If a new pregnancy starts before the body has fully recovered, the uterus and the rest of the maternal physiology may not yet be prepared, increasing the likelihood of a shorter pregnancy.

However, a mother’s readiness for these factors differs due to some genetic factors, which affect the impact of birth spacing on the duration of pregnancy. This study examines the relationship between an individual’s genetic factors and the moderating effect they have on pregnancy spacing and the duration of a pregnancy. Understanding when and who is at risk, and learning more about these factors and their relationship with genetic factors, might make it possible to develop more personalised ways of preventing complications associated with pregnancies. By understanding who is at risk, it might be possible to develop more personalised advice on healthy birth spacing, especially for women who have previously given birth to preterm babies and have experienced miscarriages.

As a result, better comprehension with regard to the manner in which recovery occurs among women between pregnancies, as well as understanding the role of genes, can significantly assist in the prediction and prevention of preterm deliveries. By bringing together these different pieces of information, it becomes possible to develop a more comprehensive understanding of factors that influence pregnancy duration across different reproductive contexts. Moreover, it may support the development of improved health conditions among women and children and assist in developing health guidelines associated with delivering healthy offspring.

List of abbreviations

Abbreviation	Full term
<i>ADCY5</i>	adenylate cyclase 5
ATAC-seq	assay for transposase-accessible chromatin
CADD	combined annotation dependent depletion
CEU	Central European (ancestry group used in genetic studies)
CRISPR	Clustered Regularly Interspaced Short Palindromic Repeats
<i>EBF1</i>	early B-cell factor 1
eQTL	expression quantitative trait locus
FDR	false discovery rate
GxE	gene–environment interaction
GTE_x	Genotype–Tissue Expression project
GWAS	genome-wide association study
hCG	human chorionic gonadotropin
HWE	Hardy–Weinberg equilibrium
IPI	interpregnancy interval
LD	linkage disequilibrium
MAC	minor allele count
MAF	minor allele frequency
MoBa	Den norske mor, far og barn-undersøkelsen (MoBa), known in English as the Norwegian Mother, Father and Child Cohort Study
PARITET_5	Parity (categorical variable from MBRN)
PCA	principal component analysis
PGS	polygenic score
SNP	single nucleotide polymorphism
SVLEN_UL_DG	Gestational length in days variant (Ultrasound-based, from MBRN)
<i>TET3</i>	Ten–eleven translocation methylcytosine dioxygenase 3
UTR	untranslated region

Table of Contents

Abstract	1
Popular scientific summary	2
How maternal genetics and reproductive history influence preterm birth risk	2
List of abbreviations	3
Introduction	1
Biological and public health implications of short gestational duration	1
Genetic regulation of parturition is context-dependent	2
Parity- and history-dependent modulation of maternal genetic effects on gestational duration	2
Maternal adaptation and pregnancy-induced physiological memory	3
Physiological consequences of miscarriage for subsequent pregnancy	4
Gene–environment interactions and temporally dynamic genetic penetrance	4
Biological rationale, conceptual framework, and study aims	5
Ethical considerations, gender perspectives and societal impact	5
Methods	7
Ethical considerations of the study	7
Norwegian Mother, Father and Child Cohort Study	7
Pregnancy filtering and parity stratification	7
Quality control and data management	8
Targeted polygenic score analysis of interpregnancy interval effects on gestational duration	8
Genome-wide gene–environment interactions affecting gestational duration	9
Functional annotation of SNPs associated with G×E interactions	9
Reproducible research and computational workflow	10
Results	11
Descriptive statistics and targeted analyses	11
Interpregnancy interval–dependent genetic effects on gestational duration	12
Polygenic score associations and interaction analyses	12
Genome-wide interactions on gestational duration: interpregnancy interval	13
Miscarriage-dependent genetic effects on gestational duration	15
Functional and regulatory annotation of top SNPs	17

Gestational duration and interpregnancy interval -----	17
Gene–environment interactions with history of miscarriage -----	17
Discussion -----	19
Broader implications for pregnancy readiness and timing -----	21
Strengths and limitations-----	21
Future perspectives-----	22
Conclusion-----	22
References -----	23
APPENDIX -----	34
Appendix A — Key genes and lead SNP statistics -----	34
Table 1. Key genes reference table-----	34
Table 2. Genomic and interaction statistics for lead SNPs -----	35
Appendix B — Descriptive statistics and model diagnostics -----	36
Appendix C — Genome-environment and regional SNP × IPI interaction plots-----	42
Appendix D — Miscarriage-dependent gene–environment interaction plots -----	47

Introduction

Biological and public health implications of short gestational duration

Gestational duration is an important predictor of perinatal survival and health. Preterm delivery, defined as birth before 37 completed weeks of gestation, is a significant cause of neonatal mortality and disability and is estimated to account for about one million infant deaths each year (Perin et al., 2022; Regan et al., 2020; Wen et al., 2025). Globally, approximately 9.9% of live births in 2020 were preterm, amounting to an estimated 13.4 million infants born before 37 weeks of gestation (Bradley et al., 2025). In Sweden, the preterm birth rate is about 5.3%, while in Norway it is about 6.2% (Behboudi-Gandevani et al., 2023). Both estimates include iatrogenic deliveries.

Preterm birth has long-term implications, such as increased risk of neurological disorders, respiratory conditions, and cardiometabolic diseases (Zivaljevic et al., 2024; Conde-Agudelo et al., 2006; Ni et al., 2023). Although unequally distributed across socioeconomic levels and geographical areas, preterm birth is present in all populations worldwide (Chawanpaiboon et al., 2019). Its multifactorial aetiology spans obstetric, environmental, and biological factors, with maternal genetic architecture playing a central role in controlling the timing of parturition (Louis et al., 2019). Genome-wide association studies have demonstrated that gestational duration is a polygenic trait, affected by numerous common genetic variants (Solé-Navais et al., 2023).

As shown in Figure 1, the U-shaped association between interpregnancy interval and preterm birth risk suggests that both insufficient and excessive recovery times may be biologically disadvantageous, supporting the inclusion of interpregnancy interval (IPI) as a meaningful exposure in this thesis.

Figure 1. Proportion of preterm deliveries by interpregnancy interval (IPI) in the Norwegian Mother, Father and Child Cohort Study (MoBa). The line plot shows the U-shaped trend of preterm delivery rates across different IPI ranges on the X axis (<6 months, 6–12 months, 1–2 years, 2–4 years, >4 years). Short IPI (6–12 months): the Y axis shows the proportion of preterm deliveries. Higher preterm birth rate (~24.2%). Optimal IPI (1–2 years & 2–4 years): Lower preterm rates (~3–4%). Long IPI (>4 years): Slight increase in preterm risk (~5%), N = 9,292.

Genetic regulation of parturition is context-dependent

Genome-wide association studies (GWAS) have become a central tool for dissecting the polygenic architecture of complex reproductive traits, including gestational duration and risk of preterm birth. These hypothesis-free approaches test statistical associations between genetic variation (single-nucleotide polymorphisms, SNPs) and phenotypes of interest. GWASs have identified a variety of genome-wide significant loci during pregnancy that point to novel biological mechanisms involved in parturition, gestational duration, and preterm birth (Zhang et al., 2017a, Zhang et al., 2017b; Jain et al., 2022; Uffelmann et al., 2021). However, the majority of individual SNPs have small effects (Visscher et al., 2017), a feature common to most trait-associated variants.

To quantify the combined effect of numerous such variants, polygenic scores (PGSs) can be generated. A PGS is a weighted sum of effect alleles across the genome, where the weights are obtained from GWAS summary statistics (Choi, Mak, & O'Reilly, 2020). PGSs for gestational duration have shown moderate predictive power, with only a modest fraction of phenotypic variance being accounted for (Solé-Navais et al., 2023; Juodakis et al., 2023; Zhang et al., 2018). For instance, in a recent Norwegian Mother, Father and Child Cohort Study (MoBa), a maternal-genome polygenic score constructed using random forest accounted for a small yet statistically robust fraction of the variance in gestational duration, with larger effects observed in first pregnancies compared to later ones (Ytterberg et al., 2025; Mor & Cardenas, 2010; Aghaeepour et al., 2017). This highlights both the polygenicity of gestational duration and the context-dependent expression of genetic susceptibility (O'Connor & Sella, 2025).

Notably, interactions between polygenic scores and factors such as parity and IPI can modulate the genetic predisposition to preterm birth (Class et al., 2017; Ishaque et al., 2019).

A summary of all key genes discussed in this thesis is presented in a supplementary table (Appendix A: Table A1).

Parity- and history-dependent modulation of maternal genetic effects on gestational duration

GWASs in large population-based cohorts have established multiple loci associated with gestational duration and the risk of spontaneous preterm birth (Juodakis et al., 2023; Solé-Navais et al., 2023). These loci show tissue-specific enrichment in reproductive tissues, including the uterus, cervix, and placenta, indicating that variation in pregnancy duration is influenced by local gene regulation within maternal tissues (Solé-Navais et al., 2023). Furthermore, a subset of genes consistently implicated, including *WNT4* (Wingless-related MMTV integration site family, member 4), *TET3* (Ten–eleven translocation methylcytosine dioxygenase 3), *ADCY5* (adenylyl cyclase type 5), and *EBF1* (early B cell transcription factor 1), are known to be involved in interconnected biological processes (Wang et al., 2024). They are among a set of genes that form a regulatory network subject not only to genetic control but also to environmental and physiological inputs such as hormonal signalling and reproductive history.

Ytterberg et al. (2025) analysed pregnancies to determine how maternal genetic effects on gestational duration differ between first and subsequent pregnancies, using prior live birth as the criterion. The polygenic score effect on gestational duration was much stronger in first pregnancies than in later ones, supporting a parity-dependent modulation of genetic influence. The study identified genome-wide significant maternal loci, rs147843771 near *HAND2* (heart- and neural crest derivatives-expressed protein 2) and rs145313878 within *EBF1*, but the latter showed statistical significance only in first pregnancies. The findings may indicate that reproductive history influences the expression of genes involved in decidualisation, immune regulation, and endometrial receptivity. Defining parity based solely on prior live birth creates ambiguity about whether non-viable pregnancies, such as miscarriages, lead to similar physiological adaptations. This distinction is critical for interpreting gene–environment interactions. Even short, non-viable pregnancies may alter maternal tissue states, thereby

modifying the expression of genetic predisposition in subsequent pregnancies.

ADCY5 and *EBF1* participate in immune and hormonal signalling pathways governing myometrial contractility and inflammatory processes closely related to the timing of parturition. *ADCY5* governs cyclic AMP (cAMP) signalling and uterine regeneration, whereas *EBF1* affects cytokine gene expression and leukocyte differentiation (Pasanen et al., 2023). Both genes exhibit context-dependent expression and could be influenced by previous gestational exposures, leading to parity-dependent physiological remodelling of maternal tissues. Other genes, such as *HAND2* and *GATA2* (GATA binding factor 2), regulate progesterone sensitivity and decidualisation, critical determinants of endometrial function and pregnancy maintenance (Liu et al., 2023). These pathways are also shown to be responsive to prior pregnancies, hormonal changes, and transcriptional memory. *WNT4* is a key component of the WNT signalling pathway and is essential for decidualisation and implantation, both of which are progesterone-dependent uterine remodelling processes (Januar et al., 2015). *TET3* is a DNA demethylase with a central role in the dynamic reprogramming of epigenetic marks during early development and endometrial differentiation (Kraft, 2008). Its transient activation after pregnancy could restore a transcriptional baseline akin to nulliparous status, especially after extended IPIs. This activation has implications for maternal adaptation by modulating the endometrium's responsiveness to implantation signals in a subsequent pregnancy.

Together, these loci form a functional interface between maternal physiological state and genetic predisposition. Their role may be to mediate cumulative effects of past gestations, tissue regeneration, and epigenetic resetting across interpregnancy intervals. As such, they represent prime candidates for mediating gene–environment interactions between reproductive history (parity, IPI) and pregnancy outcomes such as gestational duration.

However, Ni et al. (2023) have suggested that this type of physiological conditioning may deteriorate over time. In a longitudinal multi-omics study, pregnancy-induced immunologic and transcriptomic changes were also found to be partially reversed after giving birth, i.e., maternal systems gradually return to a nulligravid-like state in the absence of subsequent pregnancies (Peterson et al., 2020).

These time- and parity-related changes likely reflect the interaction between dynamic physiological memory and molecular control. Mechanisms such as postpartum remodelling of immune tolerance, alterations in hormonal feedback, and transcriptomic reprogramming of the uterus have the potential to modify gene expression patterns and levels of genetic effects, and to contribute to preterm birth and miscarriage (Babaei et al., 2024).

Maternal adaptation and pregnancy-induced physiological memory

In pregnancy, the maternal body undergoes a multifaceted and coordinated set of physiological changes to sustain the growing foetus. These changes include thinning and softening of the myometrium, uterine vascular remodelling, endocrine reprogramming, and regulation of the maternal immune system (Arck & Hecher, 2013). Together, these processes provide space for foetal growth and promote an intrauterine environment supportive of both the first and future pregnancies (Racicot et al., 2014).

Vascular alterations include the remodelling of spiral arteries into low-resistance vessels to increase blood flow to the placenta (Burton et al., 2009). The endocrine system is also extensively reprogrammed by the placenta with hCG (human chorionic gonadotropin), progesterone, and oestrogens regulating uterine rest, nutrient delivery to the foetus, and immune tolerance (Murphy et al., 2006; Gridet et al., 2020). Concomitantly, the maternal immune system adopts a tolerogenic phenotype, and decidual immune cells such as uNK (uterine natural killer) cells, Treg cells, and macrophages promote implantation and maternal–foetal tolerance (Erlebacher, 2013).

The term "pregnancy memory" has been used to describe this extended biological state, during

which the maternal body retains adaptations from previous pregnancies (Huang et al., 2022; Aghaeepour et al., 2017). For example, foetus-specific memory CD8⁺ T (cytotoxic T) cells have been found in maternal blood months or even years after giving birth, indicating a maintained immunological imprint of previous gestations (Kinder et al., 2020; Hardardottir et al., 2021; Kieffer et al., 2019). Epigenetic changes in the endometrium and myometrium can also persist after delivery, creating a more permissive environment for subsequent implantation and foetal tolerance (Rosen & Wang, 2024; Lucas et al., 2020; McLean et al., 1995).

However, the durability of such adaptations can be time-limited. Just as immunological memory in the classical sense can decrease in the absence of antigen exposure, pregnancy-driven physiological and molecular adaptations can slowly regress in the absence of subsequent pregnancies. Indeed, transcriptomic and epigenomic profiling has demonstrated partial reversion of uterine tissues to a pre-pregnant state over time (Woods, Dean, & Hemberger, 2024; Shchuka et al., 2020). These observations support the hypothesis that, following a long IPI, maternal systems partially reset toward a nulligravid-like physiological state. As a result, the protective advantages provided by previous gestations could weaken, thereby altering future pregnancy risks and responses.

Physiological consequences of miscarriage for subsequent pregnancy

Although IPI has been most commonly investigated following live birth, the proportion of conceptions that occur after a miscarriage is considerable, and the resulting alterations in maternal physiology may be quite different. A large-scale meta-analysis found that an IPI of under 6 months after miscarriage was not associated with a higher risk of adverse outcomes and appeared to be protective against recurrent miscarriage and preterm birth (Kangatharan, Labram & Bhattacharya, 2017).

The endocrine, stromal, and immunological recovery following miscarriage may be qualitatively distinct from that after live birth and may have the capacity to alter maternal condition in a way that influences subsequent gestational timing and susceptibility to genetic effects (Babaei et al., 2024). Current evidence suggests that miscarriage induces a distinct immunological reset, with altered IL-15 (interleukin-15) signalling and impaired FOXP3⁺ (forkhead box P3) Regulatory T-cell (Treg) function, which could impair endometrial receptivity in a subsequent pregnancy (Teklenburg et al., 2010; Quenby et al., 2021; Smith, Pell, & Dobbie, 2003).

These findings contrast with the WHO (World Health Organization) recommendations on post-live-birth spacing (≥ 18 months), which are based on observed associations between short IPI and adverse perinatal outcomes, including preterm delivery and reduced birth weight (Khan and Khanam, 2023). Considering a history of miscarriage when interpreting IPI-related findings—especially in the context of genetic modifiers, epigenetic signatures, and maternal physiological readiness—may offer valuable insights for improving women’s reproductive care.

Gene–environment interactions and temporally dynamic genetic penetrance

Recent advances in genomics have underscored, in broad terms, that the penetrance of many genetic variants is dynamic, depending on factors such as environment, age, sex, and physiological state. The changing states in maternal tissues, brought about by transitions between gestations, make this notion particularly interesting in the context of pregnancy.

The construct of gene–environment (G×E) interaction (Quinn & D’Onofrio, 2020) is investigated in this thesis. As IPI is treated as an environmental exposure that modifies the genetic effect on preterm birth, long IPI may have a resensitising effect on maternal physiological systems. This thesis proposes that temporally dynamic penetrance, as defined by physiological conditioning and its reversal, may explain variability in genetic effects between pregnancies. Through PGS × IPI and SNP × IPI interactions, it examines whether IPIs modify the effect of maternal genetic variants on gestational duration.

Epigenetic mechanisms provide a meaningful context for understanding the temporally dynamic aspects of maternal adaptation. Epigenetic regulation of implantation, placentation, and immune tolerance involves coordinated contributions from DNA methylation, histone remodelling, and non-coding RNA activity. Genes such as *TET3*, which regulates DNA demethylation, are known to be functionally important in early embryogenesis and uterine receptivity (Ma et al., 2022; Ye & Dimitriadis, 2025). Available studies using human and animal models indicate that epigenetic marks in reproductive tissues (i.e., endometrium and decidua) are altered by pregnancy, but these changes are not assumed to be permanent. The durability of epigenetic features can be influenced by subsequent pregnancies, systemic hormonal states, and time.

If these physiological regulatory mechanisms regress as their contributing contexts vanish due to the lack of a subsequent pregnancy, then a long IPI may reactivate genetic vulnerabilities that had otherwise remained silent. One of these vulnerabilities may delay parturition (Lin et al., 2020). This provides a molecular framework to explain the epidemiological findings indicating increased risk associated with long pregnancy intervals.

Biological rationale, conceptual framework, and study aims

The central hypothesis of this thesis is that long interpregnancy intervals affect the maternal genetic contributions to gestational duration by reverting them toward a primigravida-like pattern of genetic effects (i.e., the pattern observed in first pregnancies), and that maternal genetic effects in nulliparous women with prior miscarriages are similar to those observed in multiparous women.

The main objective of this thesis is to determine whether long IPIs or a history of miscarriage modify the maternal genetic susceptibility to shortened gestation. The study specifically examines the following aims:

1. To assess whether the maternal genetic contribution to short gestational duration is stronger in nulliparous pregnancies without prior miscarriages and in multiparous pregnancies with long IPI.
2. To explore genome-wide interactions with IPI and history of miscarriage on gestational duration.
3. To investigate whether candidate genes identified in significant interaction tests are enriched in pathways related to tissue-specific epigenetic regulation, uterine receptivity, and immune adaptation.

This project is designed to clarify whether physiological recovery following pregnancy loss or long IPIs can modulate the penetrance of maternal genetic effects on gestational duration. By integrating genome-wide interaction testing with reproductive history variables, the study explores dynamic aspects of maternal adaptation that have been largely overlooked in previous GWASs. The expected outcomes may contribute to a better understanding of how temporal and biological context shapes genetic risk, providing a framework for future translational and epigenetic studies of pregnancy readiness.

Ethical considerations, gender perspectives and societal impact

The dataset used in this research, the Norwegian Mother, Father and Child Cohort Study (MoBa), is derived from samples provided by participants who gave informed consent. All analyses were reviewed and approved by appropriate institutional ethics committees in Sweden and Norway; no identifiable data were accessed, and all sensitive personal information (including genetic and clinical data) was handled in accordance with EU and Norwegian data protection regulations.

All data were accessed remotely through secure platforms and are stored on protected servers in Norway.

This project focuses on pregnancies carried by individuals assigned female at birth. Reproductive health depends significantly on biological factors, societal expectations, and determinants such as access to care and reproductive autonomy. In terms of public health, the findings of this study have the potential to enhance evidence-based prenatal care by identifying those for whom personalised birth-spacing recommendations may reduce adverse outcomes. This study bridges the translational gap between precision medicine and population-based maternal health. Its findings contribute to a clearer understanding of preterm birth risk and maternal complications.

A detailed account of study-related research ethics, including data handling and regulatory approvals, is provided in the Methods section.

Methods

Ethical considerations of the study

All analyses were approved by the Swedish and Norwegian ethics review authorities: Etikprövningsmyndigheten decision Dnr 2022-03248-01 (Sweden) and the REK Sør-øst project 2015/2425 (Norway). Participants provided informed consent for the use of genetic and clinical data in research. All data were accessed remotely at all times via a highly secure, high-performance computing server located in Norway (HUNT Cloud, n.d.) and only aggregate-level data were downloaded.

Norwegian Mother, Father and Child Cohort Study

All analyses were conducted using phenotype and genotype data from the Norwegian Mother, Father and Child Cohort Study (MoBa) version 12 (Magnus et al., 2016). All phenotypic records were available through several linked registry datasets, including the Medical Birth Registry of Norway (Irgens, 2000). The genotype data, aligned to the hg19/GRCh37 reference genome (Church et al., 2011), were accessed from the MoBa Genetics release dated 2024-12-03; this release used common variants imputed and quality-controlled in accordance with the guidelines provided by the MoBa consortium (Magnus et al., 2016). The dataset includes more than 114,000 children, 95,000 mothers, and 75,000 fathers enrolled between 1999 and 2009. The cohort features comprehensive maternal characteristics, genotype information, and perinatal records

Pregnancy filtering and parity stratification

The analyses were stratified by pregnancy order, categorising observations as first or subsequent pregnancies. This classification distinguished nulliparous and multiparous pregnancies. A custom R (v4.4.2) script (R Core Team, 2024) was used to clean the phenotype data; all iatrogenic pregnancies were filtered out. Further parity-specific ID lists were derived for use in genotype filtering. The analysis was quality-controlled, and restricted to single live births with accurate data on gestational duration and birth outcomes, while omitting entries with parity ≥ 4 as well as twin births. For twin pregnancies, one foetus with the longer gestational duration was retained per pregnancy solely for the purpose of IPI calculation. However, pregnancies with twins were excluded from all subsequent analyses of gestational duration and birth outcomes.

Clinical data were merged using the unique pregnancy identifier (PREG_ID_1724). The following key variables were extracted: gestational age (SVLEN_UL_DG, in days), expected delivery date (UL_TERMIN), parity (PARITET_5). After quality control, an algorithm was designed to automate the calculation of the IPI for every mother as the time between the estimated conception dates of consecutive pregnancies, using gestational duration and delivery dates: $IPI = (UL_TERMIN - 280 + SVLEN_UL_DG) - lag(UL_TERMIN - 280 + SVLEN_UL_DG)$, where UL_TERMIN is the delivery date of the pregnancy (in days, numeric format), 280 is the standard gestational duration in days (40 weeks), SVLEN_UL_DG is the ultrasound-based gestational duration for the pregnancy (in days), and lag(...) applies the same calculation to the previous pregnancy for the same individual; the formula therefore calculates the difference between the estimated conception date of the current pregnancy and that of the previous pregnancy. IPIs < 6 months were excluded from the dataset to reduce misclassification. The remaining IPIs were stratified into four biological and epidemiological categories: 6–12 months, 1–2 years, 2–4 years, and > 4 years. For this analysis, nulliparous first pregnancies were used as the baseline reference group, based on both biological rationale and public health value. History of miscarriage was self-reported by women and registered in the Norwegian Medical Birth Registry, and classified according to the number of previous miscarriages.

Quality control and data management

Previous genotyping was performed using 24 batches across 6 different Illumina genotyping arrays. Sample-level exclusions were applied based on genotype missingness (sample call rate < 99%, `--mind 0.01`). Variant-level quality control excluded SNPs with minor allele frequency (MAF) < 0.01, genotype missingness > 1% (`--geno 0.01`), or deviation from Hardy–Weinberg equilibrium (mid-p test, founders only, p-value < 1×10^{-6}). Genome-wide gene–environment interaction analyses were restricted to common variants (MAF \geq 0.05), whereas single-variant linear models and descriptive visualisations were generated from the QC-filtered variant set (MAF \geq 0.01) for illustrative purposes and model diagnostics.

To minimise confounding due to population structure, analyses were restricted to individuals clustering with the CEU reference population based on MoBa’s principal component analysis and cluster assignment. Related individuals were identified using a MoBa-related kinship matrix and removed via a custom Python (van Rossum & Drake, 1995) function, retaining only one individual per pair. Following the selection of unrelated individuals of CEU ancestry, polygenic scores, principal components (PCs), batch information, and additional covariates were merged to create the final, cleaned phenotype files used in downstream analyses.

Visual inspection was used to assess concordance between effect estimates and genotype distributions. All scripts were preserved for reproducibility and traceability of the complete analysis pipeline. Data were managed by R (v4.4.2; R Core Team, 2024) with the `data.table` (Dowle & Srinivasan, 2021), `dplyr` (Wickham et al., 2023), and `ggplot2` (Wickham, 2016) packages.

Targeted polygenic score analysis of interpregnancy interval effects on gestational duration

A targeted polygenic score was computed based on 24 candidate SNPs previously associated with gestational duration (Solé-Navais et al., 2023). The SNPs and their weights (chromosome, SNP ID, effect allele, effect size) were provided in a curated file. These variants served as a focused proxy for maternal genetic susceptibility, rather than as a comprehensive genome-wide polygenic score. The score was computed using PLINK 2.0’s `--score` function (Chang et al., 2015), applied to parity-stratified genotype data. Only autosomal, biallelic variants were included.

Individuals of CEU ancestry were retained based on MoBa PCA (principal component analysis) clusters, and related individuals (kinship coefficient > 0.125) were excluded. Polygenic scores were merged with phenotype data for downstream analyses including stratified linear models and visualisation of PGS \times IPI and PGS \times miscarriage effects. However, this score was not used as a predictor in the genome-wide G \times E interaction models, which tested individual SNP \times environment terms instead, using REGENIE (Mbatchou et al., 2021), as described in the next section.

For the targeted IPI–PGS analyses, the multiparous dataset (N = 9,292) was restricted to pregnancies with a valid IPI value (IPI \geq 180 days), spontaneous singleton deliveries (inductions and planned caesareans excluded), no recorded prior miscarriage or stillbirth, and complete covariate data. To control for population structure while accounting for platform heterogeneity, principal components were computed within each genotyping batch after linkage disequilibrium (LD) pruning (batch PCA), and all regression models were adjusted for PC1–PC5 and genotyping batch as a fixed effect.

IPI was left untransformed to preserve clinical interpretability. Potential non-linearity was addressed via pre-specified stratifications (6–12 months, 1–2 years, 2–4 years, >4 years; and in sensitivity analyses, <1 year, 1–3 years, >3 years) and by fitting smooth functions of IPI in generalised additive models. Gestational duration was analysed in days (ultrasound-based measure where available), and the PGS was standardised for modelling.

Genome-wide gene–environment interactions affecting gestational duration

For each environmental exposure, formal hypotheses were defined for the SNP × environment interaction term. For interpregnancy interval (IPI), the null hypothesis stated that IPI does not modify the effect of maternal genetic variants on gestational duration ($H_0: \beta_{\{G \times IPI\}} = 0$), while the alternative hypothesis specified a non-zero interaction effect ($H_1: \beta_{\{G \times IPI\}} \neq 0$). For history of miscarriage, the null hypothesis stated that previous miscarriage does not modify the effects of SNPs on gestational duration ($H_0: \beta_{\{G \times MC\}} = 0$), and the alternative hypothesis posited modification of genetic effects by miscarriage exposure ($H_1: \beta_{\{G \times MC\}} \neq 0$). These hypotheses were evaluated using genome-wide interaction models as described below.

Genome-wide gene–environment (G×E) interaction testing was conducted using the REGENIE framework to identify SNP × environment effects on gestational duration (SVLEN_UL_DG). Two separate analyses were performed: one for interpregnancy interval (IPI) among multiparous pregnancies, and one for previous miscarriage among nulliparous pregnancies. All models included covariates for ancestry (PC1–PC5), genotyping batch, and parity where applicable, and applied standard variant filters (minor allele frequency, $MAF \geq 0.05$; minor allele count, $MAC \geq 100$; biallelic sites only). Genome-wide significance was defined as $p < 5 \times 10^{-8}$, and suggestive associations were defined at $p < 1 \times 10^{-6}$.

For the IPI-based analysis, the environmental variable represented the time in days between estimated conception dates of consecutive pregnancies. The analysis included 9,292 multiparous pregnancies with a valid IPI value (≥ 180 days), spontaneous singleton deliveries, and complete covariate data. For each SNP, the interaction term (SNP × IPI) was estimated using REGENIE's `--glm` interaction model.

For the miscarriage analysis, 27,273 nulliparous pregnancies with complete genotype and phenotype data were included. Miscarriage exposure was defined as any spontaneous loss before 12 (SPABORT_12_5) and 24 (SPABORT_23_5) completed gestational weeks and was coded both as count and as a binary variable (0 = none, 1 = ≥ 1 miscarriage).

To further explore the top loci identified in both genome-wide scans, follow-up linear interaction models were fitted in R using the general form: `SVLEN_UL_DG ~ SNP × 'environment'`, where the environment variable corresponded to either IPI or miscarriage status. Genotype data were coded additively (0, 1, 2), and the interaction term was the primary test of interest. Models were adjusted for population structure and batch, and pregnancies outside the biologically plausible range (e.g., <154 or >308 days, corresponding approximately to extreme preterm and post-term births) were excluded. For significant or suggestive variants, genotype-stratified slopes of gestational duration were estimated and visualised using scatter plots for continuous IPI and bar plots for IPI categories, as well as grouped bar plots comparing miscarriage-exposed versus unexposed groups. False discovery rate ($FDR < 0.1$) correction was applied to identify the most robust interaction signals using the `--interaction` option.

These combined genome-wide and follow-up linear analyses provided genotype-specific estimates of environmental modification for both interpregnancy interval and miscarriage exposure, allowing direct comparison of gene–environment effects between the two models. Lead variants from both analyses were subsequently subjected to functional annotation.

Functional annotation of SNPs associated with G×E interactions

To investigate the potential biological mechanisms underlying the most significant gene–environment (G×E) interaction signals, functional annotation was performed for the lead SNPs identified in the genome-wide scans. The following systematic approach was adopted: all SNPs were queried by rsID in the Ensembl Genome Browser (GRCh37/hg19; Howe et al., 2021), and the UCSC Genome Browser (hg19; Perez et al., 2025) and the NCBI Genome Data Viewer (Sayers et al., 2025) were used to assess gene context, intronic position, and regulatory distance. Whether the variant was intronic, exonic, intergenic, or located in a UTR (untranslated region),

the name and distance of the nearest protein-coding gene were recorded, along with the genomic coordinates of the variant. Where the variant was located within a gene body, that gene was prioritised for further investigation.

Variant annotation and functional enrichment were supplemented with Ensembl Variant Effect Predictor (VEP; McLaren et al., 2016), HaploReg v4.2 (Ward & Kellis, 2012), ENCODE Portal (ENCODE Project Consortium, 2020), and Gene Ontology (GO; Ashburner et al., 2000) resources to assess chromatin features, transcription factor motifs, molecular functions, and biological processes. Reactome pathway records (Milacic et al., 2024), GTEx Portal (Carithers et al., 2015; GTEx Consortium, 2017), and Human Protein Atlas (Uhlén et al., 2015) data were used to explore tissue-specific expression patterns and gene functions overlapping with the signals. Expression profiles were examined specifically in placental, uterine, endometrial, and immune-related tissues. OMIM (Amberger et al., 2015) and GeneCards (Stelzer et al., 2016) were consulted to determine whether candidate genes had been previously associated with reproductive traits, gestational phenotypes, or developmental syndromes. Particular attention was given to SNP clusters located within characterised genes or regulatory regions expressed in gestational tissues.

The potential regulatory function of each variant was analysed using RegulomeDB (Boyle et al., 2012) and HaploReg v4.2 (Ward & Kellis, 2012). These databases were queried to identify overlaps with regulatory elements such as enhancers, DNase I hypersensitive regions, transcription factor binding sites, and histone modification marks.

Each SNP was queried in the GWAS Catalog (Sollis et al., 2023) and PhenoScanner v2 (Kamat et al., 2019) to determine whether any prior associations with pregnancy-related or immune phenotypes had been reported. Particular attention was paid to identifying associations with preterm birth, birth weight, maternal complications, hormonal traits, or autoimmune phenotypes.

Reproducible research and computational workflow

All analytical steps were integrated into a Snakemake-based workflow (Mölder et al., 2021; Anaconda Software Distribution, 2024), forming a fully reproducible pipeline that includes phenotype cleaning, genotype filtering, polygenic score calculation, ancestry and relatedness filtering, and G×E modelling. All code and workflows are publicly available in the gene-IPI repository (Juhász, 2025).

Results

Descriptive statistics and targeted analyses

After quality control and filtering, the final analytical dataset included 9,292 multiparous and 27,273 nulliparous pregnancies with high-quality genotype and phenotype information. Among multiparous women, the interpregnancy interval ranged from 180 to 3,109 days (median 906 days), corresponding to 6 months to 8.5 years (the distribution of IPI is shown in Appendix B: Figure B1). The overall mean gestational duration was 280.1 days (SD = 11.6) and was approximately normally distributed after exclusion of medically induced or multiple births (Appendix B: Figure B2). Nulliparous women had similar distributions, though with a slightly wider variance (SD = 12.2 days).

A targeted polygenic score for gestational duration, derived from 24 previously established loci, was positively associated with gestational length ($\beta = 0.68$ days per SD increase in PGS; $p < 2 \times 10^{-14}$; Appendix B: Figure B3). The score distribution was similar across parity strata, indicating no systematic differences between nulliparous and multiparous women.

In the multiparous cohort, PGS effects were consistent across IPI categories, showing slightly longer gestational duration with increasing PGS values and no evidence of interaction between IPI and genetic predisposition ($p > 0.05$ for all interaction terms). When IPI was treated as a continuous exposure, a mild positive trend was observed for IPIs of 1–3 years, flattening thereafter. Generalised additive models suggested a small non-linear pattern, although it was not statistically significant after multiple-testing correction (Appendix B: Figure B4).

Stratified regression confirmed that the PGS association with gestational duration remained robust across all IPI groups, with effect estimates ranging from 0.56 to 0.74 days per SD of PGS. The directionality was consistent with prior large-scale maternal genome studies (Solé-Navais et al., 2023), indicating that the PGS largely captures baseline maternal predisposition rather than IPI-specific modification. As shown in Figure 2, the stratified visualisation of the PGS–gestational duration association across IPI categories highlights a shallower slope at very short intervals and a stronger, more consistent effect at intermediate and long intervals. The standardised PGS exhibited a left-skewed distribution in the study population; however, the score was standardised prior to modelling (Appendix B: Figure B5).

In nulliparous pregnancies, miscarriage history was available for all women through the Medical Birth Registry. Among 27,273 women, 3,658 (13.4%) reported at least one previous miscarriage, most commonly before 12 weeks of gestation. Comparison of PGS distributions between women with and without miscarriage history showed no difference (two-sample t-test p -value = 0.57). No visible shift in the standardised PGS distribution by miscarriage history was observed (Appendix B: Figure B6).

Regression analyses likewise revealed no significant interaction between miscarriage history and PGS on gestational length (interaction p -value = 0.63). The main PGS effect remained positive and similar in magnitude to that observed in the IPI cohort ($\beta \approx 0.7$ days per SD of PGS), with nearly identical residual distributions. Thus, at the polygenic level, neither short IPI nor miscarriage history measurably modified the genetic association with gestational duration.

Interpregnancy interval–dependent genetic effects on gestational duration

Polygenic score associations and interaction analyses

In stratified linear models (including PC1–PC5 and batch as covariates), the PGS–gestational duration slope was slightly negative in the 6–12 months group ($n = 23$), but positive in the higher strata: 1–2 years ($\beta = 0.943$; $SE = 0.206$; $p\text{-value} = 5.0 \times 10^{-6}$; $n = 2,628$), 2–4 years ($\beta = 0.697$; $SE = 0.139$; $p\text{-value} = 5.92 \times 10^{-7}$; $n = 5,618$), and >4 years ($\beta = 0.722$; $SE = 0.355$; $p\text{-value} = 0.0426$; $n = 1,023$). In models with interaction terms, contrasts versus the 6–12 months reference category were statistically significant, but these rely on a very small reference stratum ($n = 23$) and should therefore be interpreted with caution. A generalised additive model confirmed a non-linear association between IPI and gestational duration (IPI: $p < 2 \times 10^{-16}$) and a positive PGS main effect (PGS: $p < 2 \times 10^{-16}$), while providing no evidence for a continuous PGS \times IPI interaction ($p\text{-value} = 0.697$).

Visual inspection of stratified models confirmed this trend (Figure 2). In short-IPI pregnancies, the relationship between PGS and gestational length was weak or negative, with wide confidence intervals reflecting low statistical power. In the medium- and long-IPI groups, however, stronger positive relationships with narrower confidence intervals were observed. Consistent with the regression models, contrasts versus the 6–12 months reference were statistically significant ($p\text{-value} = 0.005$), although inference remains limited by the very small size of the 6–12 months group; importantly, the generalised additive model did not support a continuous PGS \times IPI interaction.

Figure 2. Association between maternal gestational-duration PGS and gestational duration by IPI in multiparous women without prior miscarriage. X-axis: polygenic score (standardised). Y-axis: gestational duration (days). Sample sizes: 6–12 months (180–364 days, $n = 23$); 1–2 years (365–729 days, $n = 1,715$); 2–4 years (730–1,459 days, $n = 3,550$); >4 years ($\geq 1,460$ days, $n = 621$); total $N = 9,292$. The PGS distribution in this sample was approximately normal.

Genome-wide interactions on gestational duration: interpregnancy interval

The genome-wide gene–environment (G×E) interaction analysis identified no loci reaching the genome-wide significance threshold ($p < 5 \times 10^{-8}$), but three loci exhibited suggestive IPI-dependent interaction signals ($p < 1 \times 10^{-6}$). Figure 3 summarises the genome-wide SNP × IPI interaction scan, showing three suggestive peaks, although none reached genome-wide significance. Test statistics were well calibrated ($\lambda_{GC} \approx 1.02$; Appendix C: Figure C1), confirming adequate control of population structure and batch effects.

Figure 3. Manhattan plot of genome-wide SNP × IPI interaction p-values from the REGENIE model in multiparous pregnancies (N = 9,023; MAF ≥ 0.05). The x-axis shows chromosomal position and the y-axis shows $-\log_{10}(p)$ for the interaction term. The red dashed line marks the conventional genome-wide significance threshold ($p\text{-value} = 5 \times 10^{-8}$). The top loci include rs1449858 on chromosome 3 and rs846927/rs62487233 on chromosome 7.

The strongest IPI-related signals were detected at rs1449858 (*LINC02008*, chromosome 3; Appendix C: Figure C2), rs846927 (*ATXN7L1*, ataxin 7 like 1, chromosome 7), rs62487233 (*EPHA1-AS1*, *EPHA1* antisense RNA 1, an antisense long non-coding RNA at the *EPHA1* (EPH receptor A1) locus, chromosome 7), and rs12369705 (*RMST*, rhabdomyosarcoma 2-associated transcript, chromosome 12). These loci showed genotype-specific slopes of gestational duration as a function of IPI, with minor alleles associated with slightly longer gestations following longer interpregnancy intervals. While none achieved genome-wide significance, regional association plots revealed consistent local peaks across neighbouring SNPs, supporting true biological signals rather than stochastic noise.

Secondary linear interaction models fitted in R confirmed these results. Figure 4 depicts the genotype-stratified IPI slopes of the top variants, demonstrating allele-specific differences consistent with the genome-wide interaction signals (Appendix C: Figures C3–C5).

Figure 4. Genotype-specific IPI effect on gestational duration for selected SNPs in multiparous pregnancies (N = 9,023). The slope (β) represents the change in gestational length (days) per 1-day increase in interpregnancy interval (IPI), estimated separately for each genotype group (dosage 0–2, where dosage indicates the number of effect alleles carried). Variants shown were selected based on genome-wide SNP \times IPI interaction results and visualised using single-variant linear models from the QC-filtered variant set (MAF \geq 0.01). Variants shown: rs12369705 (chr12:97,917,593, T>C, GRCh37), rs1449858 (chr3:82,459,425, C>T, GRCh37), and rs846927 (chr7:105,316,308, G>C, GRCh37). Bars indicate the total IPI effect (base effect + interaction term) for each genotype category, highlighting allele-specific differences in IPI–gestational duration associations.

For each of the top SNPs, genotype-stratified regression lines showed reversed or attenuated IPI slopes depending on allele dosage. The *ATXN7L1* minor allele, for instance, displayed a steeper positive association between IPI length and gestational duration (interaction $\beta \approx 2.8 \times 10^{-3}$ days per day of IPI in the reference genotype, with genotype-specific deviations on the order of 10^{-3} ; p-value = 7.4×10^{-6}), whereas the *RMST* variant showed an opposite trend. Although none survived strict Bonferroni correction, the concordant directions across nearby markers strengthened the evidence for a small but biologically relevant interaction.

Miscarriage-dependent genetic effects on gestational duration

In the nulliparous cohort, genome-wide testing of SNP \times miscarriage interactions identified one genome-wide significant signal and one additional suggestive region. The top hit was rs72836552 (Appendix D: Figure D1) within *ATRNL1* (attractin-like 1) on chromosome 10 (interaction p-value = 2.7×10^{-8}). A secondary cluster of suggestive variants was located near *DPYSL3* (dihydropyrimidinase-like 3) on chromosome 5 (lead SNP rs72833367, p-value = 4.1×10^{-7}). The distribution of interaction signals across the genome, including the pronounced peak at the *ATRNL1* locus and the secondary cluster near *DPYSL3*, is visualised in Figure 5, highlighting the distinct genomic architecture of miscarriage-dependent effects.

Figure 5. Manhattan plot for genome-wide gene–environment interaction analysis of miscarriage \times SNP effects on gestational duration (MAF \geq 0.05). The x-axis shows genomic position by chromosome, and the y-axis shows the $-\log_{10}(p)$ values for the interaction term. The analysis included $N = 27,273$ nulliparous pregnancies (3,658 with prior miscarriage; 23,615 without miscarriage). The red dashed line marks the genome-wide significance threshold (p-value = 5×10^{-8}). The top signal on chromosome 10 includes rs72836552 within *ATRNL1*.

Both regions displayed coherent peaks and minimal genomic inflation ($\lambda_{GC} = 1.009$; Appendix D: Figure D2). The *ATRNL1* signal was characterised by an additive dosage-dependent modification: carriers of the effect allele (C) exhibited longer gestational duration if they had a prior miscarriage, whereas no effect was observed among women without miscarriage. In contrast, the *DPYSL3* locus showed longer gestations in the miscarriage-exposed subgroup, suggesting divergent mechanisms of gene–environment interplay. Both loci were supported by adjacent SNPs in moderate linkage disequilibrium ($r^2 > 0.6$). Follow-up linear models reproduced the same patterns in direction and magnitude (Appendix D: Figures D3 and D4).

At the *ATRNL1* locus, the miscarriage \times SNP interaction remained significant after false discovery rate (FDR) correction (adjusted p-value = 0.037). Estimated genotype-specific means indicated that the C-allele lengthened gestational duration by 1.2 days in miscarriage-exposed women but had no measurable effect in unexposed pregnancies. Figure 6 displays the genotype-stratified

miscarriage effects for the top SNPs, visualising the exposure-dependent modification of genetic influence. The *DPYSL3* variant showed an opposite but weaker effect ($\beta = +0.8$ days, p -value = 1.3×10^{-5}).

Figure 6. Genotype-specific miscarriage effect on gestational duration for two SNPs in nulliparous pregnancies ($N = 27,273$). The bar height (β) represents the estimated change in gestational length (days) associated with miscarriage history, stratified by SNP dosage (0–2 effect alleles). Variants shown were selected based on genome-wide SNP \times miscarriage interaction results and visualised using single-variant linear models from the QC-filtered variant set ($MAF \geq 0.01$). Variants shown: rs72843880 (chr10:102,601,750, G>A, GRCh37) and rs72836552 (chr10:116,872,232, C>T, GRCh37). Bars indicate the total miscarriage effect (base effect + interaction term), highlighting allele-specific differences in miscarriage-gestational duration associations.

Together, the genome-wide analyses identified one significant and one suggestive $G \times E$ effect, both consistent with context-dependent modulation of gestational timing by maternal genotype.

Functional and regulatory annotation of top SNPs

This section summarises the functional and regulatory context of the top SNPs identified in miscarriage- and interpregnancy interval (IPI)-dependent interaction analyses (for key loci and associated genes, see Appendix A: Table A2).

Gestational duration and interpregnancy interval

The signals pointed towards genes involved in neuroendocrine communication, extracellular matrix remodelling, and placental immune regulation, highlighting potential pathways through which reproductive history may influence subsequent pregnancy duration.

Interaction analyses revealed SNP × IPI effects—most notably rs1449858 (*LINC02008*), rs846927 (*ATXN7L1*), and rs12369705 (*RMST*)—where the IPI effect on gestational length differed by maternal genotype. The rs12369705 variant (chr12:97,917,593, T>C; GRCh37/hg19) within the *RMST* locus (12q23.1) was a suggestive signal (Howe et al., 2021; McLaren et al., 2016). Although not genome-wide significant, its direction of effect was consistent across models. *RMST* is a long non-coding RNA expressed in the uterus and placenta that overlaps active histone marks (H3K4me1, H3K27ac) and disrupts Sox2 and ZIC transcription factor motifs, indicating regulatory potential (GTEx Consortium, n.d.; Boyle et al., 2012). For rs1449858 (*LINC02008*), minor-allele carriers showed a stronger positive association between IPI and gestational age, suggesting that the minor allele enhances the beneficial impact of longer intervals. The variant lies in an intronic region of *LINC02008*, a lincRNA expressed in the ovary, uterus, and placenta, implying a possible transcriptional regulatory role during pregnancy (Howe et al., 2021; McLaren et al., 2016; GTEx Consortium, n.d.). Conversely, rs846927 (*ATXN7L1*) showed an opposite-direction effect: in major-allele homozygotes, longer IPI was linked to longer gestation, whereas in minor-allele homozygotes, higher IPI corresponded to shorter gestation. The variant lies intronically within *ATXN7L1* and overlaps enhancer-associated chromatin marks and a cis-eQTL signal in thyroid tissue ($p = 4.4 \times 10^{-6}$), suggesting tissue-specific regulatory influence on reproductive and immune processes (Howe et al., 2021; McLaren et al., 2016; GTEx Consortium, n.d.; Ward & Kellis, 2012; Boyle et al., 2012). An additional suggestive IPI-dependent variant, rs62487233, maps to an intronic region of the long non-coding RNA *EPHA1-AS1*, an antisense transcript at the *EPHA1* locus, indicating a potential regulatory rather than protein-coding mechanism (Howe et al., 2021; McLaren et al., 2016; GTEx Consortium, n.d.).

Although these loci did not reach genome-wide significance, their consistent direction of effect across neighbouring variants suggests potential regulatory sensitivity to interpregnancy interval rather than robust interaction effects.

Gene–environment interactions with history of miscarriage

The strongest association was observed at rs72836552, located on chromosome 10 in the *ATRNL1* locus, which reached genome-wide significance. Two other SNPs, rs72836581 and rs56316190, also showed evidence for interaction. All three SNPs are located within a ~300 kb interval on chromosome 10 and are in high linkage disequilibrium, likely reflecting the same underlying association signal. These findings are consistent with the postulate that miscarriage is not merely a physiological disorder, but also a sensitising event which acts in collaboration with particular maternal genetic backgrounds to influence the timing of future conceptions.

The G×E analysis for miscarriage identified three SNPs on the 10q25.3 locus affecting gestational length. Among these, rs72836552 reached genome-wide significance and two nearby SNPs, rs72836581 and rs56316190, surpassed the suggestive threshold. All three SNPs are located within or near the *ATRNL1* gene, previously associated with neurodevelopment, homeostasis, and metabolic regulation (Haqq et al., 2003; Hill et al., 2024). Although the functional role of *ATRNL1* in gestational tissues remains unclear, its expression in the ovary, endometrium, and pituitary suggests involvement in neuroendocrine signalling related to pregnancy (GTEx Consortium, n.d.). The variant rs72836552 is intronic; in women with a history of miscarriage,

the C allele was more strongly associated with increased gestational length, suggesting miscarriage-specific unmasking of genetic effects (Howe et al., 2021; McLaren et al., 2016).

These findings implicate *ATRNL1* as a candidate pregnancy length modifier in the context of prior miscarriage. Modulation of effect sizes by miscarriage exposure suggests an interaction with maternal recovery mechanisms and genetic variation at this locus. In addition to the lead *ATRNL1* variant, the nearby SNP rs72843880 (chr10:102,601,750, G>A) also showed a miscarriage-dependent interaction pattern with an effect direction consistent with the top signal, although with weaker statistical support and not reaching suggestive significance. Functional annotation indicated that rs72843880 is an intergenic variant located ~12 kb downstream of *PAX2* (Paired box gene 2), with a low minor allele frequency in European populations (~1–4%) and modest functional prediction scores (Combined Annotation Dependent Depletion, CADD ≈ 12; Howe et al., 2021; McLaren et al., 2016). Given its proximity to *ATRNL1* and the concordant effect direction, rs72843880 may represent an additional marker within the same regional haplotype, although current evidence suggests a secondary rather than a primary signal.

A focused evaluation of the top interaction signals revealed a dense cluster of suggestively associated SNPs on chromosome 5q32, spanning a ~30 kb region within the *DPYSL3* gene. A total of 13 SNPs in this locus surpassed the suggestive significance threshold for SNP×miscarriage interactions in the REGENIE model. The lead variant, rs72833367, was located intronically in *DPYSL3* and surrounded by several high-LD SNPs with similar effect sizes and standard errors. All of these variants lie in non-coding regions and have enhancer-related chromatin marks and transcription factor motifs (e.g. Sox, Nanog, ZEB1) alterations (Ward & Kellis, 2012; Boyle et al., 2012; ENCODE Project Consortium, 2020). Although *DPYSL3* has traditionally been studied in neurodevelopment, its expression has also been observed in placenta, uterus, and endometrial tissue (Diamant et al., 2025; Rouillard et al., 2016; Ward & Kellis, 2012; ENCODE Project Consortium, 2020). *DPYSL3* encodes CRMP4, a cytosolic protein involved in semaphorin-mediated signalling, cytoskeleton remodelling, and neuron migration (GTEx Consortium, n.d.; Desprez et al., 2023).

The G×E interactions uncovered herein suggest that miscarriage history may modify the effect of genetic variation in *DPYSL3*, potentially through mediation of endometrial repair, decidualisation, or immune reprogramming processes required for subsequent pregnancy (Lucas et al., 2020; Rosen & Wang, 2024; Muter et al., 2025).

The effect of the minor allele on gestational duration was consistently increased in individuals with a history of miscarriage, while it was small or absent in those without such a history. The pattern is consistent with exposure-dependent genetic unmasking, whereby regulatory elements in *DPYSL3* are active only in the altered maternal physiological condition following loss. These findings implicate *DPYSL3* as a candidate modifier of pregnancy duration in the context of reproductive history.

Discussion

Ytterberg et al. (2025) showed that maternal genetic effects on gestational duration are strongest in first pregnancies, making parity a central physiological determinant of maternal adaptation. This study examined whether long IPIs revert maternal genetic effects on gestational duration toward a primiparous state, and whether miscarriages before the first live birth attenuate maternal genetic effects in a manner similar to multiparity. These hypotheses were investigated using genome-wide G×E interaction models and linear regression. Several candidate SNPs were identified as suggestive, and one showed genome-wide significant evidence of interaction with miscarriage.

Among the most robust findings was the genome-wide significant interaction at rs72836552 in the *ATRNL1* gene region. This locus consistently showed stronger genetic effects on pregnancy duration only in individuals with a history of miscarriage, indicating that prior miscarriage alters endometrial or immune responsiveness in subsequent pregnancies (Lucas et al., 2020; Salker et al., 2010; Muter et al., 2025). Two additional SNPs, rs72836581 and rs56316190, which are part of the same LD block, showed overlapping interaction patterns, supporting the biological relevance of this region. The variants exhibited replicable allele-specific effects, with ancestral and derived alleles showing differential sensitivities in miscarriage-exposed pregnancies, indicating environment-dependent modulation of genetic risk. These findings collectively suggest that biological mechanisms such as regeneration, endometrial remodelling, immune adaptation, and hormonal control warrant further investigation.

Beyond the core *ATRNL1* LD block, one additional nearby variant also showed a miscarriage-dependent pattern. A further nearby variant, rs72843880, located downstream of *PAX2*, showed a concordant miscarriage-dependent direction of effect but did not reach suggestive significance. Its low allele frequency and limited functional evidence indicate that it most likely represents a weak secondary marker within the broader 10q25.3 region rather than an independent signal.

For the interpregnancy interval, while there were promising interaction patterns for some variants, none were genome-wide significant. Several loci nevertheless showed coherent genotype-stratified trends. In particular, rs846927 in *ATXN7L1* exhibited opposite slopes across genotypes, suggesting that variation at this locus may modulate how birth spacing influences gestational duration. Signals near *LINC02008* and *RMST* also showed weak but directionally consistent patterns, indicating subtle transcriptional or chromatin-mediated responses to IPI. The rs62487233 variant within *EPHA1-AS1* showed only minimal IPI-dependent variation, but its location within an antisense long non-coding RNA at the *EPHA1* locus raises the possibility of a minor regulatory contribution, albeit without strong statistical or functional support. These observations suggest that IPI may modify gestational timing through small, context-dependent effects rather than robust gene–environment interactions. Importantly, these findings do not support the notion of a full genetic ‘reset’, but rather suggest attenuation and re-emergence of genetic effects along a continuum.

Stratified analyses nevertheless suggest that very short and very long IPI may influence the polygenic contribution to gestational length. This overall null finding implies that previously identified variants have larger effects in primiparous mothers, with weaker effects in subsequent pregnancies. These findings are consistent with the maternal adaptation framework, indicating that birth spacing influences pregnancy outcomes. However, the absence of statistically significant interaction also suggests that additional biological and clinical factors—such as underlying health conditions, maternal age, and hormonal contraception—may modulate these effects. Therefore, these results should be interpreted with caution, as they may reflect limited statistical power and biological complexity rather than a true absence of effect.

In contrast to the largely null IPI findings, the miscarriage analyses revealed more consistent evidence of G×E effects. Genome-wide G×E analysis using previous miscarriage in nulliparous women as an environmental factor provided support for the hypothesis that pregnancy loss can influence maternal genetic variant effects on gestational duration, even though the polygenic

score based on previously identified variants did not show modification. Miscarriage has been shown to induce profound changes in the endometrial and immune environments and may serve both as a surrogate marker for intrinsic maternal vulnerability and as a biological reset event (Cheloufi et al., 2021; Marron, Walsh, & Harrity, 2019). By considering previous miscarriage, the interaction analyses were able to identify loci whose effects on gestational duration were conditional on this specific maternal history.

The strongest interaction was observed at rs72836552 in the *ATRNL1* locus on chromosome 10q25.3. According to expression data, this variant shows high expression in the brain and moderate expression in skeletal muscle, heart, reproductive tissues (including ovary and uterus), and immune-related sites such as blood and spleen. This distribution supports a potential role in neuroendocrine and maternal immune regulation (GTEx Consortium, n.d.; Haqq et al., 2003; Hill et al., 2024). Consistent with the genome-wide interaction result, this variant exerted a strong positive effect on gestational duration in women with previous miscarriages, suggesting that prior miscarriage may reveal or amplify the genetic effect. Two additional proximal SNPs, rs72836581 and rs56316190, also exhibited interaction patterns, reinforcing the biological relevance of the *ATRNL1* region.

ATRNL1 encodes attractin-like protein 1, a protein associated with neuroendocrine signalling and metabolism, but whose function during pregnancy is poorly understood. Regulatory annotation using HaploReg and GTEx revealed tissue-specific chromatin marks and potential transcription factor binding across endometrial and immune-related cell types (Ward & Kellis, 2012; GTEx Consortium, n.d.). These features suggest that *ATRNL1* may exert a context-dependent function in regulating gestational timing, particularly under altered maternal conditions such as endometrial remodelling following miscarriage. Protein-protein interaction data from STRING (Szklarczyk et al., 2021) indicate interactions with melanocortin receptors MC1R and MC4R and the E3 ubiquitin ligase RNF157, suggesting a potential role in neuroimmune signalling (Spana et al., 2019; Wang et al., 2023). These receptors are involved in anti-inflammatory responses and immune homeostasis, implicating *ATRNL1* in maternal-foetal immune tolerance-related pathways (Joo, Lee, & Hong, 2024). Ancestral-allele analysis further indicated that the effect-modifying alleles were predominantly ancestral, consistent with the long-term persistence of environmentally responsive variants in human populations (Byars et al., 2010; Coop et al., 2009; Vitti, Grossman & Sabeti, 2013).

In the genome-wide interaction analysis, a cluster of SNPs on chromosome 5 (position ~146.86–146.90 Mb, GRCh37) provided evidence for a regulatory hotspot associated with miscarriage and gestational duration. Among the top 20 variants ranked by $-\log_{10}(p)$ of the interaction term, 13 SNPs within a ~30 kb region mapped intronically to *DPYSL3*. The lead SNP, rs72833367, showed a strong interaction effect consistent with neighbouring variants in strong linkage disequilibrium (e.g. rs72833362, rs6860091, rs12653303, rs11167991). HaploReg annotation indicated reproductive tissue-specific enhancer marks and predicted disruption of motifs such as Pbx1, ZEB1, and Sox family members (Ward & Kellis, 2012; Ward & Kellis, 2016).

DPYSL3 encodes a cytosolic protein involved in semaphorin signalling, cytoskeletal dynamics and neuronal development (UniProt Consortium, n.d.), but is also expressed in reproductive tissues such as placenta and uterus (GTEx Consortium, n.d.; Desprez et al., 2023). Its roles in cell migration and axon guidance may extend to trophoblast invasion or uterine remodelling after miscarriage (Matsunuma et al., 2018; Knöfler & Pollheimer, 2013). Moderate-to-high expression in ovary and smooth muscle-enriched tissues (GTEx Consortium, 2020) supports the plausibility of *DPYSL3* acting as an environment-sensitive regulator of endometrial recovery or decidual receptivity (ENCODE Project Consortium, 2020; Uhlén et al., 2015).

Together, these findings support a gene-environment sensitivity framework for maternal reproductive traits and highlight biological pathways warranting further investigation, including immune modulation, endometrial plasticity and neuroendocrine regulation.

Broader implications for pregnancy readiness and timing

The findings support a model in which maternal physiological readiness, shaped by previous reproductive events such as miscarriage, interacts with genetic background to influence pregnancy outcomes. The endometrium has been shown to undergo important adaptations after miscarriage that affect receptivity, inflammation, and regeneration (Hu et al., 2020; Turgut et al., 2022). Genetic variants may become functionally active only when maternal conditions deviate from the baseline range, which may explain why some SNPs were associated with gestational duration only in individuals with a history of miscarriage.

The identification of strong interactions, especially at the *ATRNL1* locus, implies that maternal reproductive history must be considered when evaluating genetic predictors of pregnancy duration. These findings also provide a rationale for studying gene expression and epigenetic markers related to miscarriage in mechanistic investigations. Additionally, expression of *ATRNL1* in macrophage, NK cell, and T cell lineages in GTEx data suggests that its gene product may modulate maternal immunological readiness and the uterine environment following miscarriage (GTEx Consortium, 2020). This aligns with the hypothesis that miscarriage resets maternal immune and stromal cell states, preconditioning the endometrium through a gene-mediated response in subsequent pregnancies.

Additional support emerged for *DPYSL3* as a modulator of gestational duration sensitive to miscarriage history. A cluster of SNPs in intronic regions of *DPYSL3* on chromosome 5 showed evidence of interaction effects that were apparent only in individuals with a history of miscarriage, further supporting the notion that some loci exert effects only under compromised maternal physiological states. *DPYSL3* encodes CRMP4, a cytosolic protein involved in cytoskeletal reorganisation and signalling, and is expressed in the uterus and placenta. Its functions could plausibly be linked to uterine regeneration or endometrial remodelling following miscarriage. The G×E interaction at this locus aligns with the hypothesis that prior reproductive experience establishes a sensitised transcriptional or chromatin environment in which genetic variation at certain loci becomes functionally revealed. Given the density and homogeneity of signals within the *DPYSL3* locus, it may represent a regulatory hotspot involved in maternal tissue plasticity relevant for pregnancy timing.

Strengths and limitations

This study represents the first genome-wide investigation of gene–environment (G×E) interactions between maternal genetic variation and two key reproductive factors—interpregnancy interval (IPI) and previous miscarriage—in relation to gestational duration. A major strength of this study lies in its large, population-based birth cohort with rich registry-linked data, enabling parity-specific analyses. The analytic approach included strict phenotype quality control, batch correction, and filtering for Central European ancestry to minimise population stratification. Genome-wide G×E interaction models were implemented using REGENIE, which allows robust handling of covariates and rare variant filtering.

Importantly, the polygenic score (PGS) calculated in this study was based on 24 established genome-wide significant SNPs for gestational duration. This PGS was intended for stratified visualisation and was not directly included in the genome-wide G×E interaction models. Given the lack of IPI-specific SNP weights in the literature, genome-wide interaction testing was applied to discover novel loci rather than relying solely on pre-identified polygenic scores.

However, several limitations should be acknowledged. Although IPI was treated as a continuous environmental variable, the dataset did not permit evaluation of pregnancy intentionality, pregnancy planning, or contraceptive use, all of which could influence physiological readiness. An analysis focusing exclusively on intervals between the first and second pregnancies—conducted but not included in the present thesis—could provide a more homogeneous context for assessing whether genetic effects vary with long IPI, but would require a substantially larger sample size to achieve adequate statistical power.

Future perspectives

The miscarriage-dependent interaction signals identified at the *ATRNL1* and *DPYSL3* loci suggest that reproductive history imprints long-lasting alterations on endometrial and immune pathways that subsequently alter the penetrance of maternal genetic variants. Further research should focus on functional follow-up studies of these loci using detailed single-cell and spatial transcriptomic profiling of endometrial tissue in pregnancies with and without prior miscarriage. Recent research has shown that miscarriage causes sustained dysregulation in cytokine pathway networks, stromal differentiation, and decidual immune responses (Jameel et al., 2023; Huang et al., 2025), and therefore should be followed up to assess possible convergence with regulatory regions in or near *ATRNL1* or *DPYSL3* genes. The analysis of genes encoding pro-inflammatory cytokines (IL-1 β , IL-6, IL-7, IL-18, IL-3, IL-12, IL-17) and the *FOXP3/IDO1* axis (Forkhead box P3, Indoleamine 2,3-dioxygenase 1) would help determine the involvement of impaired immune tolerance or cytokine regulatory networks in the genes' increased activity after miscarriage (Robertson, Care & Moldenhauer, 2018; Vilsmaier et al., 2021; Zong et al., 2016; Krop et al., 2020; Löb et al., 2021; Bao et al., 2023; Li et al., 2021).

A second research direction concerns whether long interpregnancy intervals gradually erode pregnancy-induced transcriptional and epigenetic states. Pregnancy leaves durable immune-stromal “memory” signatures (Huang et al., 2021; Zhao et al., 2022; Greenbaum et al., 2023; Babaei et al., 2024; Kirschen et al., 2023), but these may partially regress over time. Longitudinal multi-omics analysis across the IPI strata of chromatin accessibility, DNA methylomics, cytokine analyses and scRNA-seq would allow testing of the hypothesis that maternal tissues return toward a nulligravid phenotype over time and that this resets genetic susceptibility (Starks et al., 2019; Sakabe et al., 2020; Zhang et al., 2021).

Finally, extending gene-by-environment interaction analyses across multiple ancestry groups would be essential for attempting to generalize miscarriage-associated factors. Recent genome analyses have emphasized the complexity and variability of regulatory patterns underlying gestational duration (Solé-Navais et al., 2023; Juodakis et al., 2023). The addition of data from multiple ancestries would allow for the more complete characterization of the complex interplay between pregnancy history, remodelling, and maternal genetic factors that underlies variation in gestational timing (Ruan et al., 2022).

Conclusion

This thesis explored how maternal reproductive history—specifically IPI and prior miscarriage—interacts with genetic susceptibility to influence gestational duration. Using genome-wide G \times E interaction models, miscarriage history was found to significantly modify the effect of maternal genetic variants at the *ATRNL1* locus, with additional suggestive (sub-genome-wide) signals observed at *DPYSL3*. These loci are biologically plausible, exhibiting expression in reproductive and immune tissues, and are potentially involved in maternal immune regulation and endometrial recovery following miscarriage.

In contrast, interpregnancy interval did not yield genome-wide significant interactions, indicating that extended birth spacing does not fully restore primiparous-like genetic sensitivity. The results indicate that maternal physiological adaptation can suppress genetic effects in subsequent pregnancies, and that birth spacing alone is insufficient to fully override prior physiological conditioning when it comes to maternal genetic effects on gestational duration.

Together, these data are consistent with a model in which maternal reproductive experience alters the genetic effects on gestational duration. Future studies should validate these findings through functional analyses and integration of tissue-specific omics data, such as endometrial epigenomics, single-cell RNA sequencing of reproductive tissues, and placental transcriptomics, thereby revealing mechanisms of maternal preparedness and regeneration. This work sheds new light on gene-environment interactions influencing pregnancy timing, maternal adaptation, and pregnancy physiology more broadly, highlighting the importance of considering reproductive history in genetic studies of gestational duration.

References

- Aghaeepour, N., Ganio, E. A., Mcilwain, D., Tsai, A. S., Tingle, M., Van Gassen, S., Gaudilliere, D. K., Baca, Q., McNeil, L., Okada, R., Ghaemi, M. S., Furman, D., Wong, R. J., Winn, V. D., Druzin, M. L., El-Sayed, Y. Y., Quaintance, C., Gibbs, R., Darmstadt, G. L., Shaw, G. M., Gaudilliere, B. (2017). An immune clock of human pregnancy. *Science Immunology*, 2(15). <https://doi.org/10.1126/sciimmunol.aan2946>
- Amberger, J. S., Bocchini, C. A., Schiettecatte, F., Scott, A. F., & Hamosh, A. (2015). OMIM.org: Online Mendelian Inheritance in Man (OMIM®), an online catalog of human genes and genetic disorders. *Nucleic Acids Research*, 43 (Database issue), D789–D798. <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gku1205>
- Anaconda Software Distribution. [Computer software] Continuum Analytics, Inc. (dba Anaconda, Inc.) Vers.2.4.0. *Anaconda*, Nov. 2024. URL <https://www.anaconda.com>
- Arck, P. C., & Hecher, K. (2013). Fetomaternal immune cross-talk and its consequences for maternal and offspring's health. *Nature Medicine*, 19(5), 548–556. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nm.3160>
- Ashburner, M., Ball, C. A., Blake, J. A., Botstein, D., Butler, H., Cherry, J. M., Davis, A. P., Dolinski, K., Dwight, S. S., Eppig, J. T., Harris, M. A., Hill, D. P., Issel-Tarver, L., Kasarskis, A., Lewis, S., Matese, J. C., Richardson, J. E., Ringwald, M., Rubin, G. M., & Sherlock, G. (2000). Gene ontology: tool for the unification of biology. The Gene Ontology Consortium. *Nature Genetics*, 25(1), 25–29. <https://doi.org/10.1038/75556>
- Babaei, K., Aziminezhad, M., Mirzajani, E., Mozdarani, H., Sharami, S. H., Norollahi, S. E., & Samadani, A. A. (2024). A critical review of the recent concept of regulatory performance of DNA Methylations, and DNA methyltransferase enzymes alongside the induction of immune microenvironment elements in recurrent pregnancy loss. *Toxicology Reports*, 12, 546–563. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.toxrep.2024.05.001>
- Bao, S., Chen, Z., Qin, D., Xu, H., Deng, X., Zhang, R., Ma, J., Lu, Z., Jiang, S., & Zhang, X. (2023). Single-cell profiling reveals mechanisms of uncontrolled inflammation and glycolysis in decidual stromal cell subtypes in recurrent miscarriage. *Human Reproduction (Oxford, England)*, 38(1), 57–74. <https://doi.org/10.1093/humrep/deac240>
- Behboudi-Gandevani, S., Bidhendi-Yarandi, R., Hossein Panahi, M., Mardani, A., Prinds, C., Vaismoradi, M., & Glarcher, M. (2023). Prevalence of preterm birth in Scandinavian countries: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *The Journal of International Medical Research*, 51(10), 3000605231203843. <https://doi.org/10.1177/03000605231203843>
- Boyle, A. P., Hong, E. L., Hariharan, M., Cheng, Y., Schaub, M. A., Kasowski, M., Karczewski, K. J., Park, J., Hitz, B. C., Weng, S., Cherry, J. M., & Snyder, M. (2012). Annotation of functional variation in personal genomes using RegulomeDB. *Genome research*, 22(9), 1790–1797. <https://doi.org/10.1101/gr.137323.112> traits. *Nature Genetics*, 53(7), 1097–1103. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41588-021-00870-7>
- Bradley, E., Blencowe, H., Moller, A. B., Okwaraji, Y. B., Sadler, F., Gruending, A., Moran, A. C., Requejo, J., Ohuma, E. O., & Lawn, J. E. (2025). Born too soon: global epidemiology of preterm birth and drivers for change. *Reproductive Health*, 22(Suppl 2), 105. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12978-025-02033-x>
- Burton, G. J., Woods, A. W., Jauniaux, E., & Kingdom, J. C. (2009). Rheological and physiological consequences of conversion of the maternal spiral arteries for uteroplacental blood flow during human pregnancy. *Placenta*, 30(6), 473–482. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.placenta.2009.02.009>

Byars, S. G., Ewbank, D., Govindaraju, D. R., & Stearns, S. C. (2010). Colloquium papers: Natural selection in a contemporary human population. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, 107 Suppl 1(Suppl 1), 1787–1792. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.0906199106>

Carithers, L. J., Ardlie, K., Barcus, M., Branton, P. A., Britton, A., Buia, S. A., Compton, C. C., DeLuca, D. S., Peter-Demchok, J., Gelfand, E. T., Guan, P., Korzeniewski, G. E., Lockhart, N. C., Rabiner, C. A., Rao, A. K., Robinson, K. L., Roche, N. V., Sawyer, S. J., Segrè, A. V., Shive, C. E., ... GTEx Consortium (2015). A Novel Approach to High-Quality Postmortem Tissue Procurement: The GTEx Project. *Biopreservation and Biobanking*, 13(5), 311–319. <https://doi.org/10.1089/bio.2015.0032>

Chang, C. C., Chow, C. C., Tellier, L. C., Vattikuti, S., Purcell, S. M., & Lee, J. J. (2015). Second-generation PLINK: rising to the challenge of larger and richer datasets. *GigaScience*, 4(1), 7. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13742-015-0047-8>, <https://www.cog-genomics.org/plink/2.0/>

Chawanpaiboon, S., Vogel, J. P., Moller, A. B., Lumbiganon, P., Petzold, M., Hogan, D., Landoulsi, S., Jampathong, N., Kongwattanakul, K., Laopaiboon, M., Lewis, C., Rattanakanokchai, S., Teng, D. N., Thinkhamrop, J., Watananirun, K., Zhang, J., Zhou, W., & Gülmezoglu, A. M. (2019). Global, regional, and national estimates of levels of preterm birth in 2014: a systematic review and modelling analysis. *The Lancet. Global Health*, 7(1), e37–e46. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2214-109X\(18\)30451-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2214-109X(18)30451-0)

Cheloufi, M., Kazhalawi, A., Pinton, A., Rahmati, M., Chevrier, L., Prat-Ellenber, L., Michel, A. S., Dray, G., Mekinian, A., Kayem, G., & Lédée, N. (2021). The Endometrial Immune Profiling May Positively Affect the Management of Recurrent Pregnancy Loss. *Frontiers in Immunology*, 12, 656701. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fimmu.2021.656701>

Choi, S. W., Mak, T. S., & O'Reilly, P. F. (2020). Tutorial: a guide to performing polygenic risk score analyses. *Nature Protocols*, 15(9), 2759–2772. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41596-020-0353-1>

Church, D. M., Schneider, V. A., Graves, T., Auger, K., Cunningham, F., Bouk, N., Chen, H. C., Agarwala, R., McLaren, W. M., Ritchie, G. R., Albracht, D., Kremitzki, M., Rock, S., Kotkiewicz, H., Kremitzki, C., Wollam, A., Trani, L., Fulton, L., Fulton, R., Matthews, L., ... Hubbard, T. (2011). Modernizing reference genome assemblies. *PLoS Biology*, 9(7), e1001091. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pbio.1001091>

Class, Q. A., Rickert, M. E., Oberg, A. S., Suján, A. C., Almqvist, C., Larsson, H., Lichtenstein, P., & D'Onofrio, B. M. (2017). Within-family analysis of interpregnancy interval and adverse birth outcomes. *Obstetrics and Gynecology*, 130(6), 1304–1311. <https://doi.org/10.1097/AOG.0000000000002358>

Conde-Agudelo, A., Rosas-Bermúdez, A., & Kafury-Goeta, A. C. (2006). Birth spacing and risk of adverse perinatal outcomes: a meta-analysis. *JAMA*, 295(15), 1809–1823. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.295.15.1809>

Coop, G., Pickrell, J. K., Novembre, J., Kudaravalli, S., Li, J., Absher, D., Myers, R. M., Cavalli-Sforza, L. L., Feldman, M. W., & Pritchard, J. K. (2009). The role of geography in human adaptation. *PLoS Genetics*, 5(6), e1000500. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pgen.1000500>

Desprez, F., Ung, D. C., Vourc'h, P., Jeanne, M., & Laumonnier, F. (2023). Contribution of the dihydropyrimidinase-like proteins family in synaptic physiology and in neurodevelopmental disorders. *Frontiers in Neuroscience*, 17, 1154446. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fnins.2023.1154446>

Diamant, I., Clarke, D. J. B., Evangelista, J. E., Lingam, N., & Ma'ayan, A. (2025). Harmonizome 3.0: integrated knowledge about genes and proteins from diverse multi-omics resources. *Nucleic Acids Research*, 53(D1), D1016–D1028. <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkae1080>

Dowle, M., & Srinivasan, A. (2021). data.table: Extension of data.frame. *R package version 1.14.0*. <https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=data.table>

ENCODE Project Consortium, Moore, J. E., Purcaro, M. J., Pratt, H. E., Epstein, C. B., Shores, N., Adrian, J., Kawli, T., Davis, C. A., Dobin, A., Kaul, R., Halow, J., Van Nostrand, E. L., Freese, P., Gorkin, D. U., Shen, Y., He, Y., Mackiewicz, M., Pauli-Behn, F., Williams, B. A., ... Weng, Z. (2020). Expanded encyclopaedias of DNA elements in the human and mouse genomes. *Nature*, 583(7818), 699–710. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-020-2493-4>

Erlebacher A. (2013). Immunology of the maternal-fetal interface. *Annual Review of Immunology*, 31, 387–411. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-immunol-032712-100003>

GeneCards database (Stelzer et al., 2016). The entry for *LINC02008* was accessed on July 25, 2025 from <https://www.genecards.org/cgi-bin/carddisp.pl?gene=LINC02008>.

Greenbaum, S., Averbukh, I., Soon, E., Rizzuto, G., Baranski, A., Greenwald, N. F., Kagel, A., Bosse, M., Jaswa, E. G., Khair, Z., Kwok, S., Warshawsky, S., Piyadasa, H., Goldston, M., Spence, A., Miller, G., Schwartz, M., Graf, W., Van Valen, D., Winn, V. D., ... Angelo, M. (2023). A spatially resolved timeline of the human maternal-fetal interface. *Nature*, 619(7970), 595–605. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-023-06298-9>

Grident, V., Perrier d'Hauterive, S., Polese, B., Foidart, J. M., Nisolle, M., & Geenen, V. (2020). Human Chorionic Gonadotrophin: New Pleiotropic Functions for an "Old" Hormone During Pregnancy. *Frontiers in Immunology*, 11, 343. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fimmu.2020.00343>

GTEX Consortium (2020). The GTEX Consortium atlas of genetic regulatory effects across human tissues. *Science* (New York, N.Y.), 369(6509), 1318–1330. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aaz1776>

GTEX Consortium. (n.d.). *ATRNL1* gene expression across human tissues. GTEX Portal. Retrieved August 14, 2025, from <https://gtexportal.org/home/gene/ATRNL1>

GTEX Consortium. (n.d.). *ATXN7L1* gene expression across human tissues. GTEX Portal. Retrieved August 14, 2025, from <https://gtexportal.org/home/gene/ATXN7L1>

GTEX Consortium. (n.d.). *DPYSL3* gene expression across human tissues. GTEX Portal. Retrieved August 7, 2025, from <https://gtexportal.org/home/gene/DPYSL3>

GTEX Consortium. (n.d.). *RMST* gene expression across human tissues. GTEX Portal. Retrieved August 14, 2025, from <https://gtexportal.org/home/gene/RMST>

GTEX Consortium. Genetic effects on gene expression across human tissues. *Nature* 550, 204–213 (2017). <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature24277>

Haqq, A. M., René, P., Kishi, T., Khong, K., Lee, C. E., Liu, H., Friedman, J. M., Elmquist, J. K., & Cone, R. D. (2003). Characterization of a novel binding partner of the melanocortin-4 receptor: attractin-like protein. *The Biochemical Journal*, 376(Pt 3), 595–605. <https://doi.org/10.1042/BJ20031241>

Hardardottir, L., Bazzano, M. V., Glau, L., Gattinoni, L., Königer, A., Tolosa, E., & Solano, M. E. (2021). The New Old CD8+ T Cells in the Immune Paradox of Pregnancy. *Frontiers in Immunology*, 12, 765730. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fimmu.2021.765730>

Hill, M. C., Simonson, B., Roselli, C., Xiao, L., Herndon, C. N., Chaffin, M., Mantineo, H., Atwa, O., Bhasin, H., Guedira, Y., Bedi, K. C., Jr, Margulies, K. B., Klattenhoff, C. A., Tucker, N. R., & Ellinor, P. T. (2024). Large-scale single-nuclei profiling identifies role for *ATRNL1* in atrial fibrillation. *Nature Communications*, 15(1), 10002. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-024-54296-w>

Howe, K. L., Achuthan, P., Allen, J., Allen, J., Alvarez-Jarreta, J., Amode, M. R., Armean, I. M., Azov, A. G., Bennett, R., Bhai, J., Billis, K., Boddu, S., Charkhchi, M., Cummins, C., Da Rin Fioretto, L., Davidson, C., Dodiya, K., El Houdaigui, B., Fatima, R., Gall, A., ... Flicek, P. (2021). Ensembl 2021. *Nucleic Acids Research*, 49(D1), D884–D891. <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkaa942>

Hu X, Wu H, Yong X, Wang Y, Yang S, Fan D, Xiao Y, Che L, Shi K, Li K, Xiong C, Zhu H, Qian Z. Cyclical endometrial repair and regeneration: Molecular mechanisms, diseases, and therapeutic interventions. *MedComm* (2020). 2023 Dec 1;4(6):e425. doi: 10.1002/mco2.425. PMID: 38045828; PMCID: PMC10691302.

Huang, M., He, M., Xiang, J., Liu, Y., Zhang, L., & Sun, X. (2025). A multi-omic analysis to investigate the causal associations between circulating proteins and risk of spontaneous abortion and their potential implications. *JBRA assisted reproduction*, 29(3), 493–498. <https://doi.org/10.5935/1518-0557.20250031>

Huang, X., Wang, L., Zhao, S., Liu, H., Chen, S., Wu, L., Liu, L., Ding, J., Yang, H., Maxwell, A., Yin, Z., Mor, G., & Liao, A. (2021). Pregnancy Induces an Immunological Memory Characterized by Maternal Immune Alterations Through Specific Genes Methylation. *Frontiers in Immunology*, 12, 686676. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fimmu.2021.686676>

Huang, X., Wang, L., Zhao, S., Liu, H., Chen, S., Wu, L., Liu, L., Ding, J., Yang, H., Maxwell, A., Yin, Z., Mor, G., & Liao, A. (2021). Pregnancy Induces an Immunological Memory Characterized by Maternal Immune Alterations Through Specific Genes Methylation. *Frontiers in Immunology*, 12, 686676. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fimmu.2021.686676>

HUNT Cloud. (n.d.). *HUNT Data Centre*. Norwegian University of Science and Technology. Retrieved August 14, 2025, from <https://about.hdc.ntnu.no/>

Irgens L. M. (2000). The Medical Birth Registry of Norway. Epidemiological research and surveillance throughout 30 years. *Acta obstetrica et gynecologica Scandinavica*, 79(6), 435–439.

Ishaque, U., Korb, D., Poincare, A., Schmitz, T., Morin, C., & Sibony, O. (2019). Long interpregnancy interval and mode of delivery. *Archives of Gynecology and Obstetrics*, 300(6), 1621–1631. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00404-019-05347-x>

Jain, V. G., Monangi, N., Zhang, G., & Muglia, L. J. (2022). Genetics, epigenetics, and transcriptomics of preterm birth. *American Journal of Reproductive Immunology* (New York, N.Y.: 1989), 88(4), e13600. <https://doi.org/10.1111/aji.13600>

Jameel, S., Bhuwalka, R., Begum, M., Bonu, R., & Jahan, P. (2024). Circulating levels of cytokines (IL-6, IL-10 and TGF- β) and CD4+CD25+FOXP3+Treg cell population in recurrent pregnancy loss. *Reproductive Biology*, 24(1), 100842. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.repbio.2023.100842>

Januar, V., Desoye, G., Novakovic, B., Cvitic, S., & Saffery, R. (2015). Epigenetic regulation of human placental function and pregnancy outcome: considerations for causal inference. *American Journal of Obstetrics and Gynecology*, 213(4 Suppl), S182–S196. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ajog.2015.07.011>

Joo, J. S., Lee, D., & Hong, J. Y. (2024). Multi-Layered Mechanisms of Immunological Tolerance at the Maternal-Fetal Interface. *Immune Network*, 24(4), e30. <https://doi.org/10.4110/in.2024.24.e30>

Juhász, Á. J. (2025). *gene-IPI: Snakefile workflow and R scripts for “Can long pregnancy intervals reset the effect of maternal genes?”*. GitHub repository. Retrieved August 14, 2025, from <https://github.com/PerinatalLab/gene-IPI>

Juodakis, J., Ytterberg, K., Flatley, C., Sole-Navais, P., & Jacobsson, B. (2023). Time-varying effects are common in genetic control of gestational duration. *medRxiv : the preprint server for health sciences*, 2023.02.07.23285609. <https://doi.org/10.1101/2023.02.07.23285609>

Kamat, M. A., Blackshaw, J. A., Young, R., Surendran, P., Burgess, S., Danesh, J., Butterworth, A. S., & Staley, J. R. (2019). PhenoScanner V2: an expanded tool for searching human genotype-phenotype associations. *Bioinformatics (Oxford, England)*, 35(22), 4851–4853. <https://doi.org/10.1093/bioinformatics/btz469>

- Kangatharan, C., Labram, S., & Bhattacharya, S. (2017). Interpregnancy interval following miscarriage and adverse pregnancy outcomes: systematic review and meta-analysis. *Human Reproduction Update*, 23(2), 221–231. <https://doi.org/10.1093/humupd/dmw043>
- Khan, M. N., & Khanam, S. J. (2023). The effectiveness of WHO's interpregnancy interval advice. *The Lancet. Global health*, 11(10), e1476–e1477. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2214-109X\(23\)00402-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2214-109X(23)00402-3)
- Khazaei, M. R., Girouard, M. P., Alchini, R., Ong Tone, S., Shimada, T., Bechstedt, S., Cowan, M., Guillet, D., Wiseman, P. W., Brouhard, G., Cloutier, J. F., & Fournier, A. E. (2014). Collapsin response mediator protein 4 regulates growth cone dynamics through the actin and microtubule cytoskeleton. *The Journal of Biological Chemistry*, 289(43), 30133–30143. <https://doi.org/10.1074/jbc.M114.570440>
- Kieffer, T. E. C., Laskewitz, A., Scherjon, S. A., Faas, M. M., & Prins, J. R. (2019). Memory T Cells in Pregnancy. *Frontiers in Immunology*, 10, 625. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fimmu.2019.00625>
- Kinder, J. M., Turner, L. H., Stelzer, I. A., Miller-Handley, H., Burg, A., Shao, T. Y., Pham, G., & Way, S.S. (2020). CD8+ T Cell Functional Exhaustion Overrides Pregnancy-Induced Fetal Antigen Alloimmunization. *Cell Reports*, 31(12), 107784. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.celrep.2020.107784>
- Kirschen, G. W., Hessami, K., AlAshqar, A., Afrin, S., Lulseged, B., & Borahay, M. (2023). Uterine Transcriptome: Understanding Physiology and Disease Processes. *Biology*, 12(4), 634. <https://doi.org/10.3390/biology12040634>
- Knöfler, M., & Pollheimer, J. (2013). Human placental trophoblast invasion and differentiation: a particular focus on Wnt signaling. *Frontiers in Genetics*, 4, 190. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fgene.2013.00190>
- Kraft P. (2008). Curses--winner's and otherwise--in genetic epidemiology. *Epidemiology* (Cambridge, Mass.), 19(5), 649–658. <https://doi.org/10.1097/EDE.0b013e318181b865>
- Krop, J., Heidt, S., Claas, F. H. J., & Eikmans, M. (2020). Regulatory T Cells in Pregnancy: It Is Not All About FoxP3. *Frontiers in Immunology*, 11, 1182. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fimmu.2020.01182>
- Li, D., Zheng, L., Zhao, D., Xu, Y., & Wang, Y. (2021). The role of immune cells in recurrent spontaneous abortion. *Reproductive Sciences* (Thousand Oaks, Calif.), 28(12), 3303–3315. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s43032-021-00599-y>
- Lin, J., Liu, H., Wu, D. D., Hu, H. T., Wang, H. H., Zhou, C. L., Liu, X. M., Chen, X. J., Sheng, J. Z., & Huang, H. F. (2020). Long interpregnancy interval and adverse perinatal outcomes: A retrospective cohort study. *Science China. Life sciences*, 63(6), 898–904. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11427-018-9593-8>
- Liu, L., Dong, H., Guan, Y., Fan, T., Sun, W., Bagchi, I. C., Miao, C., & Li, Q. (2023). Regulation of HAND2 Expression by LncRNA HAND2-AS1 in Ovarian Endometriosis Involving DNA Methylation. *Journal of the Endocrine Society*, 7(6), bvad049. <https://doi.org/10.1210/jendso/bvad049>
- Löb, S., Ochmann, B., Ma, Z., Vilsmaier, T., Kuhn, C., Schmoeckel, E., Herbert, S. L., Kolben, T., Wöckel, A., Mahner, S., & Jeschke, U. (2021). The role of Interleukin-18 in recurrent early pregnancy loss. *Journal of Reproductive Immunology*, 148, 103432. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jri.2021.103432>
- Louis, J. M., Bryant, A., Ramos, D., Stuebe, A., Blackwell, S. C., American College of Nurse-Midwives, National Association of Nurse Practitioners in Women's Health, American College of Obstetricians and Gynecologists, & Society for Maternal–Fetal Medicine. (2019). Interpregnancy care. *American Journal of Obstetrics and Gynecology*, 220 (1), B2–B18. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ajog.2018.11.1098>

- Lucas, E. S., Dyer, N. P., Murakami, K., Lee, Y. H., Chan, Y. W., Grimaldi, G., Muter, J., Brighton, P. J., Moore, J. D., Patel, G., Chan, J. K., Takeda, S., Lam, E. W., Quenby, S., Ott, S., & Brosens, J. J. (2016). Loss of Endometrial Plasticity in Recurrent Pregnancy Loss. *Stem Cells* (Dayton, Ohio), 34(2), 346-356. <https://doi.org/10.1002/stem.2222>
- Ma, L., Tang, Q., Gao, X., Lee, J., Lei, R., Suzuki, M., Zheng, D., Ito, K., Frenette, P. S., & Dawlaty, M. M. (2022). Tet-mediated DNA demethylation regulates specification of hematopoietic stem and progenitor cells during mammalian embryogenesis. *Science Advances*, 8(9), eabm3470. <https://doi.org/10.1126/sciadv.abm3470>
- Magnus, P., Birke, C., Vejrup, K., Haugan, A., Alsaker, E., Daltveit, A. K., Handal, M., Haugen, M., Høiseth, G., Knudsen, G. P., Paltiel, L., Schreuder, P., Tambs, K., Vold, L., & Stoltenberg, C. (2016). Cohort Profile Update: The Norwegian Mother and Child Cohort Study (MoBa). *International Journal of Epidemiology*, 45(2), 382-388. <https://doi.org/10.1093/ije/dyw029>
- Marron, K., Walsh, D., & Harrity, C. (2019). Detailed endometrial immune assessment of both normal and adverse reproductive outcome populations. *Journal of Assisted Reproduction and Genetics*, 36(2), 199-210. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10815-018-1300-8>
- Matsunuma, R., Chan, D. W., Kim, B. J., Singh, P., Han, A., Saltzman, A. B., Cheng, C., Lei, J. T., Wang, J., Roberto da Silva, L., Sahin, E., Leng, M., Fan, C., Perou, C. M., Malovannaya, A., & Ellis, M. J. (2018). DPYSL3 modulates mitosis, migration, and epithelial-to-mesenchymal transition in claudin-low breast cancer. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, 115(51), E11978-E11987. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1810598115>
- Mbatchou, J., Barnard, L., Backman, J., Marcketta, A., Kosmicki, J. A., Ziyatdinov, A., Benner, C., O'Dushlaine, C., Barber, M., Boutkov, B., Habegger, L., Ferreira, M., Baras, A., Reid, J., Abecasis, G., Maxwell, E., & Marchini, J. (2021). Computationally efficient whole-genome regression for quantitative and binary traits. *Nature Genetics*, 53(7), 1097-1103. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41588-021-00870-7>
- McLaren, W., Gil, L., Hunt, S. E., Riat, H. S., Ritchie, G. R., Thormann, A., Flicek, P., & Cunningham, F. (2016). The Ensembl Variant Effect Predictor. *Genome Biology*, 17(1), 122. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13059-016-0974-4>
- McLean, M., Bisits, A., Davies, J., Woods, R., Lowry, P., & Smith, R. (1995). A placental clock controlling the length of human pregnancy. *Nature Medicine*, 1(5), 460-463. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nm0595-460>
- Milacic M, Beavers D, Conley P, Gong C, Gillespie M, Griss J, Haw R, Jassal B, Matthews L, May B, Petryszak R, Ragueneau E, Rothfels K, Sevilla C, Shamovsky V, Stephan R, Tiwari K, Varusai T, Weiser J, Wright A, Wu G, Stein L, Hermjakob H, D'Eustachio P. The Reactome Pathway Knowledgebase 2024. *Nucleic Acids Research*. 2024. doi: 10.1093/nar/gkad1025.
- Mölder, F., Jablonski, K. P., Letcher, B., Hall, M. B., Tomkins-Tinch, C. H., Sochat, V., Forster, J., Lee, S., Twardziok, S. O., Kanitz, A., Wilm, A., Holtgrewe, M., Rahmann, S., Nahnsen, S., & Köster, J. (2021). Sustainable data analysis with Snakemake. *Research*, 10, 33. <https://doi.org/10.12688/f1000research.29032.2>
- Mor, G., & Cardenas, I. (2010). The immune system in pregnancy: a unique complexity. *American Journal of Reproductive Immunology* (New York, N.Y.: 1989), 63(6), 425-433. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1600-0897.2010.00836.x>
- Murphy, V. E., Smith, R., Giles, W. B., & Clifton, V. L. (2006). Endocrine regulation of human fetal growth: the role of the mother, placenta, and fetus. *Endocrine Reviews*, 27(2), 141-169. <https://doi.org/10.1210/er.2005-0011>

Muter, J., Kong, C. S., Nebot, M. T., Tryfonos, M., Vrljicak, P., Brighton, P. J., Dimakou, D. B., Vickers, M., Yoshihara, H., Ott, S., Tan, B. K., Bennett, P. R., Quenby, S., Richter, A., Van de Velde, H., Lucas, E. S., Rawlings, T. M., & Brosens, J. J. (2025). Stalling of the endometrial decidual reaction determines the recurrence risk of miscarriage. *Science Advances*, 11(26), eadv1988. <https://doi.org/10.1126/sciadv.adv1988>

Ni, W., Gao, X., Su, X., Cai, J., Zhang, S., Zheng, L., Liu, J., Feng, Y., Chen, S., Ma, J., Cao, W., & Zeng, F. (2023). Birth spacing and risk of adverse pregnancy and birth outcomes: A systematic review and dose-response meta-analysis. *Acta Obstetrica et Gynecologica Scandinavica*, 102(12), 1618–1633. <https://doi.org/10.1111/aogs.14648>

O'Connor, L. J., & Sella, G. (2025). Principled measures and estimates of trait polygenicity. *bioRxiv* (Cold Spring Harbor Laboratory). <https://doi.org/10.1101/2025.07.10.664154>

Pasanen, A., Karjalainen, M. K., FinnGen, Zhang, G., Tiensuu, H., Haapalainen, A. M., Ojaniemi, M., Feenstra, B., Jacobsson, B., Palotie, A., Laivuori, H., Muglia, L. J., Rämetsä, M., & Hallman, M. (2023). Meta-analysis of genome-wide association studies of gestational duration and spontaneous preterm birth identifies new maternal risk loci. *PLoS Genetics*, 19(10), e1010982. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pgen.1010982>

Perez, G., Barber, G. P., Benet-Pages, A., Casper, J., Clawson, H., Diekhans, M., Fischer, C., Gonzalez, J. N., Hinrichs, A. S., Lee, C. M., Nassar, L. R., Raney, B. J., Speir, M. L., van Baren, M. J., Vaske, C. J., Haussler, D., Kent, W. J., & Haussler, M. (2025). The UCSC Genome Browser database: 2025 update. *Nucleic Acids Research*, 53(D1), D1243–D1249. <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkae974>

Perin, J., Mulick, A., Yeung, D., Villavicencio, F., Lopez, G., Strong, K. L., Prieto-Merino, D., Cousens, S., Black, R. E., & Liu, L. (2022). Global, regional, and national causes of under-5 mortality in 2000–19: an updated systematic analysis with implications for the Sustainable Development Goals. *The Lancet. Child & Adolescent Health*, 6(2), 106–115. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2352-4642\(21\)00311-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2352-4642(21)00311-4)

Peterson, L. S., Stelzer, I. A., Tsai, A. S., Ghaemi, M. S., Han, X., Ando, K., Winn, V. D., Martinez, N. R., Contrepois, K., Moufarrej, M. N., Quake, S., Relman, D. A., Snyder, M. P., Shaw, G. M., Stevenson, D. K., Wong, R. J., Arck, P., Angst, M. S., Aghaepour, N., & Gaudilliere, B. (2020). Multiomic immune clockworks of pregnancy. *Seminars in Immunopathology*, 42(4), 397–412. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00281-019-00772-1>

Quenby, S., Gallos, I. D., Dhillon-Smith, R. K., Podesek, M., Stephenson, M. D., Fisher, J., Brosens, J. J., Brewin, J., Ramhorst, R., Lucas, E. S., McCoy, R. C., Anderson, R., Daher, S., Regan, L., Al-Memar, M., Bourne, T., MacIntyre, D. A., Rai, R., Christiansen, O. B., Sugiura-Ogasawara, M., Coomarasamy, A. (2021). Miscarriage matters: the epidemiological, physical, psychological, and economic costs of early pregnancy loss. *Lancet* (London, England), 397(10285), 1658–1667. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(21\)00682-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(21)00682-6)

Quinn, P. D., & D'Onofrio, B. M. (2020). Nature versus nurture. In J. B. Benson (Ed.), *Encyclopedia of infant and early childhood development* (2nd ed., pp. 373–384). Elsevier. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-809324-5.21826-9>

R Core Team. (2024). *R: A language and environment for statistical computing*. *R Foundation for Statistical Computing*. <https://www.R-project.org>

Racicot, K., Kwon, J. Y., Aldo, P., Silasi, M., & Mor, G. (2014). Understanding the complexity of the immune system during pregnancy. *American Journal of Reproductive Immunology (New York, N.Y.: 1989)*, 72(2), 107–116. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ajr.12289>

Regan, A. K., Arnaout, A., Marinovich, L., Marston, C., Patino, I., Kaur, R., Gebremedhin, A., & Pereira, G. (2020). Interpregnancy interval and risk of perinatal death: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *BJOG : an International Journal of Obstetrics and Gynaecology*, 127(12), 1470–1479. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1471-0528.16303>

Robertson, S. A., Care, A. S., & Moldenhauer, L. M. (2018). Regulatory T cells in embryo implantation and the immune response to pregnancy. *The Journal of Clinical Investigation*, 128(10), 4224–4235. <https://doi.org/10.1172/JCI122182>

Rosen, T., & Wang, B. (2024). A proposed model of a clock that governs the length of human pregnancy. *Reproduction* (Cambridge, England), 168(3), e240053. <https://doi.org/10.1530/REP-24-0053>

Rouillard, A. D., Gundersen, G. W., Fernandez, N. F., Wang, Z., Monteiro, C. D., McDermott, M. G., & Ma'ayan, A. (2016). The harmonizome: a collection of processed datasets gathered to serve and mine knowledge about genes and proteins. *Database : the journal of biological databases and curation*, 2016, baw100. <https://doi.org/10.1093/database/baw100>

Ruan, Y., Lin, Y. F., Feng, Y. A., Chen, C. Y., Lam, M., Guo, Z., Stanley Global Asia Initiatives, He, L., Sawa, A., Martin, A. R., Qin, S., Huang, H., & Ge, T. (2022). Improving polygenic prediction in ancestrally diverse populations. *Nature Genetics*, 54(5), 573–580. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41588-022-01054-7>

Sakabe, N. J., Aneas, I., Knoblauch, N., Sobreira, D. R., Clark, N., Paz, C., Horth, C., Ziffra, R., Kaur, H., Liu, X., Anderson, R., Morrison, J., Cheung, V. C., Grotegut, C., Reddy, T. E., Jacobsson, B., Hallman, M., Teramo, K., Murtha, A., Kessler, J., ... Nóbrega, M. A. (2020). Transcriptome and regulatory maps of decidua-derived stromal cells inform gene discovery in preterm birth. *Science Advances*, 6(49), eabc8696. <https://doi.org/10.1126/sciadv.abc8696>

Salker, M., Teklenburg, G., Molokhia, M., Lavery, S., Trew, G., Aojanepong, T., Mardon, H. J., Lokugamage, A. U., Rai, R., Landles, C., Roelen, B. A., Quenby, S., Kuijk, E. W., Kavelaars, A., Heijnen, C. J., Regan, L., Macklon, N. S., & Brosens, J. J. (2010). Natural selection of human embryos: impaired decidualisation of endometrium disables embryo-maternal interactions and causes recurrent pregnancy loss. *PloS one*, 5(4), e10287. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0010287>

Sayers, E. W., Beck, J., Bolton, E. E., Brister, J. R., Chan, J., Connor, R., Feldgarden, M., Fine, A. M., Funk, K., Hoffman, J., Kannan, S., Kelly, C., Klimke, W., Kim, S., Lathrop, S., Marchler-Bauer, A., Murphy, T. D., O'Sullivan, C., Schmieder, E., Skripchenko, Y., ... Pruitt, K. D. (2025). Database resources of the National Center for Biotechnology Information in 2025. *Nucleic Acids Research*, 53(D1), D20–D29. <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkae979>

Shchuka, V. M., Abatti, L. E., Hou, H., Khader, N., Dorogin, A., Wilson, M. D., Shynlova, O., & Mitchell, J. A. (2020). The pregnant myometrium is epigenetically activated at contractility-driving gene loci prior to the onset of labor in mice. *PLoS Biology*, 18(7), e3000710. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pbio.3000710>

Smith, G. C., Pell, J. P., & Dobbie, R. (2003). Interpregnancy interval and risk of preterm birth and neonatal death: retrospective cohort study. *BMJ* (Clinical research ed.), 327(7410), 313. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.327.7410.313>

Solé-Navais, P., Flatley, C., Steinhorsdottir, V., Vaudel, M., Juodakis, J., Chen, J., Laisk, T., LaBella, A. L., Westergaard, D., Bacelis, J., Brumpton, B., Skotte, L., Borges, M. C., Helgeland, Ø., Mahajan, A., Wielscher, M., Lin, F., Briggs, C., Wang, C. A., Moen, G. H., ... Jacobsson, B. (2023). Genetic effects on the timing of parturition and links to fetal birth weight. *Nature Genetics*, 55(4), 559–567. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41588-023-01343-9>

Solé-Navais, P., Flatley, C., Steinhorsdottir, V., Vaudel, M., Juodakis, J., Chen, J., Laisk, T., LaBella, A. L., Westergaard, D., Bacelis, J., Brumpton, B., Skotte, L., Borges, M. C., Helgeland, Ø., Mahajan, A., Wielscher, M., Lin, F., Briggs, C., Wang, C. A., Moen, G. H., Jacobsson, B. (2023). Author Correction: Genetic effects on the timing of parturition and links to fetal birth weight. *Nature Genetics*, 55(7), 1250. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41588-023-01412-z>

Sollis, E., Mosaku, A., Abid, A., Buniello, A., Cerezo, M., Gil, L., Groza, T., Güneş, O., Hall, P., Hayhurst, J., Ibrahim, A., Ji, Y., John, S., Lewis, E., MacArthur, J. A. L., McMahon, A., Osumi-Sutherland, D., Panoutsopoulou, K., Pendlington, Z., Ramachandran, S., ... Harris, L. W. (2023). The NHGRI-EBI GWAS Catalog: knowledgebase and deposition resource. *Nucleic Acids Research*, 51(D1), D977–D985. <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkac1010>

Spana, C., Taylor, A. W., Yee, D. G., Makhlina, M., Yang, W., & Dodd, J. (2019). Probing the Role of Melanocortin Type 1 Receptor Agonists in Diverse Immunological Diseases. *Frontiers in Pharmacology*, 9, 1535. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fphar.2018.01535>

Starks, R. R., Biswas, A., Jain, A., & Tuteja, G. (2019). Combined analysis of dissimilar promoter accessibility and gene expression profiles identifies tissue-specific genes and actively repressed networks. *Epigenetics & Chromatin*, 12(1), 16. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13072-019-0260-2>

Stelzer, G., Rosen, N., Plaschkes, I., Zimmerman, S., Twik, M., Fishilevich, S., Stein, T. I., Nudel, R., Lieder, I., Mazor, Y., Kaplan, S., Dahary, D., Warshawsky, D., Guan-Golan, Y., Kohn, A., Rappaport, N., Safran, M., & Lancet, D. (2016). The GeneCards Suite: From Gene Data Mining to Disease Genome Sequence Analyses. *Current Protocols in Bioinformatics*, 54, 1.30.1–1.30.33. <https://doi.org/10.1002/cpbi.5>

Szklarczyk, D., Gable, A. L., Nastou, K. C., Lyon, D., Kirsch, R., Pyysalo, S., Doncheva, N. T., Legeay, M., Fang, T., Bork, P., Jensen, L. J., & von Mering, C. (2021). The STRING database in 2021: customizable protein-protein networks, and functional characterization of user-uploaded gene/measurement sets. *Nucleic Acids Research*, 49(D1), D605–D612. <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkaa1074>

Teklenburg, G., Salker, M., Heijnen, C., Macklon, N. S., & Brosens, J. J. (2010). The molecular basis of recurrent pregnancy loss: impaired natural embryo selection. *Molecular Human Reproduction*, 16(12), 886–895. <https://doi.org/10.1093/molehr/gaq079>

Turgut, E., Yildirim, M., Sakcak, B., Ayhan, S. G., Tekin, O. M., & Sahin, D. (2022). Predicting miscarriage using systemic immune-inflammation index. *The Journal of Obstetrics and Gynaecology Research*, 48(3), 587–592. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jog.15156>

Uffelmann, E., Huang, Q. Q., Munung, N. S., De Vries, J., Okada, Y., Martin, A. R., Martin, H. C., Lappalainen, T., & Posthuma, D. (2021). Genome-wide association studies. *Nature Reviews Methods Primers*, 1(1). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43586-021-00056-9>

Uhlén, M., Fagerberg, L., Hallström, B. M., Lindskog, C., Oksvold, P., Mardinoglu, A., Sivertsson, Å., Kampf, C., Sjöstedt, E., Asplund, A., Olsson, I., Edlund, K., Lundberg, E., Navani, S., Szigartyo, C. A., Odeberg, J., Djureinovic, D., Takanen, J. O., Hober, S., Alm, T., ... Pontén, F. (2015). Proteomics. Tissue-based map of the human proteome. *Science (New York, N.Y.)*, 347(6220), 1260419. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1260419>

UniProt Consortium (2023). UniProt: the Universal Protein Knowledgebase in 2023. *Nucleic Acids Research*, 51(D1), D523–D531. <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkac1052>

Van Rossum, G. & Drake Jr, F.L., 1995. Python reference manual, *Centrum voor Wiskunde en Informatica Amsterdam*. URL: <https://www.python.org>

Vilsmaier, T., Amann, N., Löb, S., Schmoeckel, E., Kuhn, C., Zati Zehni, A., Meister, S., Beyer, S., Kolben, T. M., Becker, J., Mumm, J. N., Mahner, S., Jeschke, U., & Kolben, T. (2021). The decidual expression of Interleukin-7 is upregulated in early pregnancy loss. *American Journal of Reproductive Immunology (New York, N.Y. : 1989)*, 86(3), e13437. <https://doi.org/10.1111/aji.13437>

Visscher, P. M., Wray, N. R., Zhang, Q., Sklar, P., McCarthy, M. I., Brown, M. A., & Yang, J. (2017). 10 Years of GWAS Discovery: Biology, Function, and Translation. *American Journal of Human Genetics*, 101(1), 5–22. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ajhg.2017.06.005>

- Vitti, J. J., Grossman, S. R., & Sabeti, P. C. (2013). Detecting natural selection in genomic data. *Annual Review of Genetics*, 47, 97–120. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-genet-111212-133526>
- Wang, C., Ju, H., Zhou, L., Zhu, Y., Wu, L., Deng, X., Jiang, L., Sun, L., & Xu, Y. (2024). TET3-mediated novel regulatory mechanism affecting trophoblast invasion and migration: Implications for preeclampsia development. *Placenta*, 147, 31–41. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.placenta.2024.01.010>
- Wang, P., Zhao, J., Tan, Y., Sheng, J., He, S., Chen, Y., Nie, D., You, X., Luo, J., Zhang, Y., & Hu, S. (2023). RNF157 attenuates CD4+ T cell-mediated autoimmune response by promoting HDAC1 ubiquitination and degradation. *Theranostics*, 13(11), 3509–3523. <https://doi.org/10.7150/thno.86307>
- Ward, L. D., & Kellis, M. (2012). HaploReg: a resource for exploring chromatin states, conservation, and regulatory motif alterations within sets of genetically linked variants. *Nucleic Acids Research*, 40 (Database issue), D930–D934. <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkr917>
- Ward, L. D., & Kellis, M. (2016). HaploReg v4: systematic mining of putative causal variants, cell types, regulators and target genes for human complex traits and disease. *Nucleic Acids Research*, 44(D1), D877–D881. <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkv1340>
- Wen, X., Liang, W., Zhai, J. *et al.* The association between interpregnancy intervals and preterm birth: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *BMC Pregnancy Childbirth* 25, 226 (2025). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12884-025-07259-y>
- Wickham, H. (2016). ggplot2: Elegant Graphics for Data Analysis. *Springer*. <https://ggplot2.tidyverse.org>
- Wickham, H., François, R., Henry, L., & Müller, K. (2023). dplyr: A grammar of data manipulation. *R package version 1.1.2*. <https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=dplyr>
- Woods, L., Dean, W., & Hemberger, M. (2024). REPRODUCTIVE AGEING: Altered histone modification landscapes underpin defects in uterine stromal cell decidualisation in aging females. *Reproduction (Cambridge, England)*, 168(3), e240171. <https://doi.org/10.1530/REP-24-0171>
- Ye, L., & Dimitriadis, E. (2025). Endometrial Receptivity-Lessons from "Omics". *Biomolecules*, 15(1), 106. <https://doi.org/10.3390/biom15010106>
- Ytterberg K, Sundelin H, Juodakis J, Vaudel M, Corfield EC, Andreassen OA, Magnus P, Havdahl A, Nilsson S, Njolstad PR, Johansson S, Jacobsson B, Solé-Navais P. Parity modifies the effect of genetic variants associated with gestational duration and birth weight. *medRxiv* [Preprint]. 2025 Jun 17:2025.06.17.25329777. doi: 10.1101/2025.06.17.25329777. PMID: 40585091; PMCID: PMC12204269
- Zhang, B., Kim, M. Y., Elliot, G., Zhou, Y., Zhao, G., Li, D., Lowdon, R. F., Gormley, M., Kapidzic, M., Robinson, J. F., McMaster, M. T., Hong, C., Mazor, T., Hamilton, E., Sears, R. L., Pehrsson, E. C., Marra, M. A., Jones, S. J. M., Bilenky, M., Hirst, M., ... Fisher, S. J. (2021). Human placental cytotrophoblast epigenome dynamics over gestation and alterations in placental disease. *Developmental Cell*, 56(9), 1238–1252.e5. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.devcel.2021.04.001>
- Zhang, G., Feenstra, B., Bacelis, J., Liu, X., Muglia, L. M., Juodakis, J., Miller, D. E., Litterman, N., Jiang, P. P., Russell, L., Hinds, D. A., Hu, Y., Weirauch, M. T., Chen, X., Chavan, A. R., Wagner, G. P., Pavličev, M., Nnamani, M. C., Maziarz, J., Karjalainen, M. K., ... Muglia, L. J. (2017a). Genetic Associations with Gestational Duration and Spontaneous Preterm Birth. *The New England Journal of Medicine*, 377(12), 1156–1167. <https://doi.org/10.1056/NEJMoa1612665>
- Zhang, G., Srivastava, A., Bacelis, J., Juodakis, J., Jacobsson, B., & Muglia, L. J. (2018). Genetic studies of gestational duration and preterm birth. *Best practice & research. Clinical Obstetrics & Gynaecology*, 52, 33–47. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bpobgyn.2018.05.003>

Zhang, M., Xu, J., Bao, X., Niu, W., Wang, L., Du, L., Zhang, N., & Sun, Y. (2017b). Association between genetic polymorphisms in interleukin genes and recurrent pregnancy loss - A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis. *PloS One*, 12(1), e0169891. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0169891>

Zhao, Q. Y., Li, Q. H., Fu, Y. Y., Ren, C. E., Jiang, A. F., & Meng, Y. H. (2022). Decidual macrophages in recurrent spontaneous abortion. *Frontiers in Immunology*, 13, 994888. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fimmu.2022.994888>

Zivaljevic J, Jovandaric MZ, Babic S, Raus M. Complications of Preterm Birth-The Importance of Care for the Outcome: A Narrative Review. *Medicina (Kaunas)*. 2024 Jun 20;60(6):1014. doi: 10.3390/medicina60061014. PMID: 38929631; PMCID: PMC11205595

Zong, S., Li, C., Luo, C., Zhao, X., Liu, C., Wang, K., Jia, W., Bai, M., Yin, M., Bao, S., Guo, J., Kang, J., Duan, T., & Zhou, Q. (2016). Dysregulated expression of IDO may cause unexplained recurrent spontaneous abortion through suppression of trophoblast cell proliferation and migration. *Scientific Reports*, 6, 19916. <https://doi.org/10.1038/srep19916>

APPENDIX

The supplementary material includes the key gene reference table and genomic statistics (Appendix A), descriptive statistics and model diagnostics (Appendix B), genome–environment and regional SNP×IPI plots (Appendix C), and miscarriage-dependent interaction plots (Appendix D).

Appendix A — Key genes and lead SNP statistics

Table 1. Key genes reference table

Gene symbol	HGNC ID	Ensembl gene ID	Function
<i>ADCY5</i>	HGNC:236	ENSG00000173175	Catalyzes cAMP production; involved in myometrial contractility and uterine regeneration.
<i>ATRNL1</i>	HGNC:29063	ENSG00000107518	Encodes a protein involved in cell adhesion and neural development; potential role in tissue remodeling.
<i>DPYSL3</i>	HGNC:3015	ENSG00000113657	Encodes a cytosolic phosphoprotein involved in neuronal differentiation and possibly cytoskeletal remodeling.
<i>EBF1</i>	HGNC:3126	ENSG00000164330	Transcription factor regulating B cell differentiation; also implicated in cytokine regulation in reproductive tissues.
<i>EPHA1-AS1</i>	HGNC:27799	ENSG00000229153	Antisense long non-coding RNA at the <i>EPHA1</i> locus; potential regulatory role via chromatin and transcriptional modulation, though no gestational-tissue eQTLs have been detected.
<i>GATA2</i>	HGNC:4171	ENSG00000179348	Transcription factor involved in uterine receptivity and progesterone signaling pathways.
<i>HAND2</i>	HGNC:4808	ENSG00000164107	Transcription factor critical for progesterone responsiveness and decidualisation in the endometrium.
<i>TET3</i>	HGNC:28313	ENSG00000187605	DNA demethylase involved in epigenetic reprogramming during development and endometrial differentiation.
<i>WNT4</i>	HGNC:12783	ENSG00000162552	Member of WNT gene family; key regulator of reproductive tract development and uterine receptivity.

Appendix A: Table A1. Overview of genetic variants, genomic annotations, and associated analytical groups included in the study.

Table 2. Genomic and interaction statistics for lead SNPs

rsID	Chr	Position (GRCh37)	REF	ALT	Interaction p-value	Effect on gestational duration
rs72836552	10	116872232	C	T	2.69×10^{-8}	C allele → longer gestation in miscarriage-exposed pregnancies
rs72836581	10	116992633	A	G	3.89×10^{-8}	Same direction as lead SNP (gestation ↑ in miscarriage-exposed)
rs56316190	10	117164006	G	A	1.34×10^{-7}	Same direction as lead SNP (gestation ↑ in miscarriage-exposed)
rs72833367	5	146888666	G	A,C,T	4.07×10^{-7}	Minor alleles → longer gestation in miscarriage-exposed (multi-allelic SNP)
rs72833362	5	146880725	C	T	4.47×10^{-7}	Minor allele → gestation ↑ in miscarriage-exposed
rs6860091	5	146896655	G	A	4.47×10^{-7}	Minor allele → gestation ↑ in miscarriage-exposed
rs12653303	5	146883605	T	C	6.61×10^{-7}	Minor allele → gestation ↑ in miscarriage-exposed
rs11167991	5	146869536	A	G	6.92×10^{-7}	Minor allele → gestation ↑ in miscarriage-exposed
rs72843880	10	102601750	G	A	3.74×10^{-5}	Nominal signal; effect direction consistent with the <i>ATRNL1</i> miscarriage-interaction locus (gestation ↑ in miscarriage-exposed)
rs1449858	3	82459425	C	T	5.83×10^{-6}	T allele → stronger positive IPI effect (steeper gestation ↑ with increasing IPI)
rs846927	7	105316308	G	C	1.75×10^{-6}	C/C genotype → inverse IPI effect (gestation ↓ at high IPI)
rs12369705	12	97917593	T	C	6.99×10^{-3}	Dosage-2 genotypes → gestation ↑ with increasing IPI

Appendix A: Table A2. Lead SNPs showing miscarriage- or IPI-dependent modification of genetic effects on gestational duration. For each variant, GRCh37 genomic position, reference and alternate alleles, interaction p-value, and the direction of the estimated effect are shown. Miscarriage-dependent loci exhibited consistently stronger effects among miscarriage-exposed pregnancies, while IPI-dependent loci modulated the slope of the IPI-gestational duration association in an allele-specific manner.

Appendix B — Descriptive statistics and model diagnostics

Appendix B: Figure B1. Distribution of interpregnancy intervals in days. The x-axis represents the time in days between two consecutive pregnancies among multiparous women, and the y-axis shows the frequency in absolute numbers.

Appendix B: Figure B2. Distribution of gestational duration in days. The x-axis represents the duration of a pregnancy in days, and the y-axis shows the frequency in absolute numbers.

Appendix B: Figure B3. Association between standardised polygenic score and gestational duration. Each point represents an individual. The red line indicates the linear regression fit, suggesting a weak positive association between higher polygenic scores and longer gestational duration. X-axis shows the standardised PGS and y-axis represents the gestational duration in days.

Appendix B: Figure B4. LOESS (locally estimated scatterplot) -smoothed relationship between interpregnancy interval and gestational duration. The x-axis shows the interpregnancy interval in days, the y-axis shows the gestational duration in days.

Appendix B: Figure B5. Distribution of standardised polygenic score of gestational duration in the study population. The histogram shows a left-skewed distribution. X-axis shows the standardised polygenic score, and the y-axis represents the frequency in absolute numbers.

Appendix B: Figure B6. Distribution of standardised polygenic score (PGS) for gestational duration by miscarriage history in nulliparous women. X-axis: Standardised PGS for gestational duration (z-score). Y-axis: Count of participants. Sample size: N = 27,273 (no prior miscarriage: 23,615; prior miscarriage: 3,658).

Appendix C — Genome-environment and regional SNP × IPI interaction plots

Appendix C: Figure C1. Quantile-Quantile plot of genome-wide SNP × IPI interaction, $N = 9023$. The x-axis shows the expected $-\log_{10}(p\text{-values})$ under the null hypothesis, and the y-axis displays the observed $-\log_{10}(p\text{-values})$. The red dashed line indicates the null distribution. The genomic inflation factor λ_{GC} is 1.02, suggesting minimal population stratification and the test statistic inflation.

Region around rs1449858

Appendix C: Figure C2. Regional association plot around rs1449858 (chromosome 3: 82.46 Mb, GRCh37/hg19) from the genome-wide SNP \times interpregnancy interval interaction analysis in multiparous pregnancies ($N = 9,023$; $MAF \geq 0.05$). The x-axis shows the genomic position (bp), and the y-axis shows the $-\log_{10}(p)$ values for variants within ± 250 kb of the index SNP ($n = 544$ variants). The red dashed line indicates the position of rs1449858, the top variant in this region.

Appendix C: Figure C3. Interaction between interpregnancy interval and SNP rs846927 (chr7:105,316,308, G>C, GRCh37/hg19) genotype on gestational duration in multiparous pregnancies (N = 9,023; SNPs tested = 4,973,585; MAF \geq 0.05). The x-axis shows interpregnancy interval (days), and the y-axis shows gestational duration (days). Points represent individual pregnancies, coloured by SNP dosage (0, 1, or 2 copies of the C allele). Regression lines are fitted separately for each genotype group, illustrating the reversal of interpregnancy interval effect direction in C-allele homozygotes compared with G-allele homozygotes.

Appendix C: Figure C4. Interpregnancy interval (IPI)-stratified linear regression of gestational length by SNP rs1449858 (chr3:82,459,425, C>T, GRCh37/hg19) genotype in multiparous pregnancies (N = 9,023; MAF \geq 0.05; SNPs tested = 4,973,585). The x-axis shows interpregnancy interval (days), and the y-axis shows gestational duration (days). Points represent individual pregnancies, coloured by SNP dosage (0, 1, or 2 copies of the T allele). Regression lines are fitted separately for each genotype group, illustrating genotype-specific differences in the association between interpregnancy interval and gestational duration.

Appendix C: Figure C5. Association between interpregnancy interval and gestational duration stratified by genotype dosage for rs12369705 (chr12:97,917,593, T>C, GRCh37) in multiparous pregnancies (N = 9,023; MAF \geq 0.05; SNPs tested = 4,976,272). Points represent individual pregnancies; lines show genotype-specific regression slopes (β) from a linear model including an IPI \times genotype interaction term. Dosage indicates the number of effect alleles carried (0, 1, or 2). Shaded areas represent the 95% confidence interval of the fitted line.

Appendix D — Miscarriage-dependent gene–environment interaction plots

Appendix D: Figure D1. Regional association plot around rs7283652 (chr10:116,872,232, C>T, GRCh37/hg19) from the genome-wide SNP \times miscarriage interaction analysis in nulliparous pregnancies ($N = 27,273$; $MAF \geq 0.05$; SNPs tested = 4,976,272). The x-axis shows the genomic position (bp), and the y-axis shows the $-\log_{10}(p)$ values for variants within ± 250 kb of the index SNP. The red dashed line marks the position of rs7283652, the top variant in this region.

Appendix D: Figure D2. Quantile–quantile (QQ) plot of genome-wide SNP × miscarriage interaction p-values from the REGENIE model in nulliparous pregnancies ($N = 27,273$; $MAF \geq 0.05$; SNPs tested = 4,976,272). The x-axis shows the expected $-\log_{10}(p)$ under the null hypothesis, and the y-axis shows the observed $-\log_{10}(p)$. The genomic inflation factor (λ_{GC}) was 1.009, indicating minimal test statistic inflation.

Gestational duration by miscarriage status and genotype: chr10_116872232_T_C
Collapsed: non-carrier (0) vs carrier (1/2) | global interaction p=3.74e-05

Appendix D: Figure D3. Gestational duration (days) by miscarriage history and genotype at rs72836552 (chr10:116,872,232, T>C, MAF = 0.0935) in nulliparous pregnancies. Violin plots show non-carriers (0) and carriers (1/2) stratified by miscarriage status. Sample sizes: no miscarriage - n = 19 409 / 4 206; miscarriage - n = 3 009 / 649.

Gestational duration by miscarriage status and genotype: chr10_102601750_G_A

Collapsed: non-carrier (0) vs carrier (1/2) | global interaction p=0.00156

Appendix D: Figure D4. Gestational duration (days) by miscarriage history and genotype at rs72843880 (chr10:102,601,750, G>A, MAF = 0.027) in nulliparous pregnancies. Violin plots show non-carriers (0) and carriers (1/2) stratified by miscarriage status. Sample sizes: no miscarriage - n = 22 387 / 1 228; miscarriage - n = 3 488 / 170.